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REPORT
SECOND EDITION

Global Data Barometer

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Data for Development

Contents

4	Acknowledgements
8	Introduction
11	Key Findings
14	Methodology Methodological Changes Geographical Scope Structure Data Collection Scoring and Calculation
27	Core Areas of Analysis Governance Foundations Critical Competencies
49	Thematic Areas of Analysis Availability

85 **Cross-cutting Analysis**

Data Foundations for AI

Inclusion

Use of Data

99 **Regional Analysis**

Latin America and the Caribbean

Africa

112 **Final Observations**

115 **Annexes**

Annex 1-Scoring Methodology

Annex 2-Capabilities Groups

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*** Disclaimer**

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This report reflects data collected between **August 31, 2022, and September 1, 2024.**

Users applying AI tools to datasets from the Global Data Barometer should exercise caution and remain mindful of AI's limitations. AI-generated results do not replace expert analysis and must be carefully interpreted and validated.

Introduction

The global data landscape is at a pivotal juncture. While data holds unprecedented promise for tackling major global challenges, from strengthening public integrity and driving inclusive economic development to enabling responsible innovation in Artificial Intelligence (AI), access to high-quality, usable data is becoming increasingly constrained. Scholars like [Verhulst](#) (2024) have warned of a “data winter”, a period marked by growing limitations in data access, weakened accountability mechanisms, and fragmented regulatory frameworks. These developments threaten not only innovation but the very foundations of democratic resilience and public trust.

This new edition of the Global Data Barometer (GDB) is being released at a time when the responsible use of data and AI must be balanced against intensifying concerns about opacity and inequality. As AI systems grow more embedded in public life, the risks associated with the use of biased, incomplete, or inaccessible data multiply, undermining efforts to serve the public interest and exacerbating existing inequalities. Meanwhile, democratic backsliding is raising the stakes on ensuring open, participatory data systems, essential for ensuring civic oversight in the digital age.

Healthy data ecosystems are essential, yet the Barometer’s findings reveal that while many countries are improving data governance and making progress on transparency, implementation remains uneven. Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC) generally exhibits stronger foundational capabilities than Africa, but both regions face critical challenges in sustaining open data, building interoperability, and equipping public officials with the skills needed to govern and reuse data effectively. Alarming, as government-led open data initiatives decline and AI guidance remains largely absent from national frameworks, the gap between aspiration and action continues to grow.

The 2nd Edition of the Global Data Barometer provides the evidence needed to increase our understanding of this evolving landscape, having assessed 43 countries against newly refined indicators and cross-cutting themes, such as AI and Inclusion, while continuing to track core elements like data governance, data protection, and data management.

Ultimately, this report is not just about measuring progress. It is a tool for critically examining how data shapes power. It aims to help governments, civil society, and researchers design more equitable, transparent, and accountable data systems that not only mitigate harm but actively promote social cohesion, trust, and democratic renewal.

About the Barometer

The Global Data Barometer builds on the legacy of the Open Data Barometer (ODB) that was published between 2013 and 2020 and is hosted by the Data for Development Network (D4D.net).

The results of the 1st Edition of the Global Data Barometer (hereafter, the Barometer) were published in 2022. This 2nd Edition of the Barometer builds upon the methodology used for the 1st Edition, reflecting insights and feedback, as well as an ever-evolving data landscape. It draws on primary data based on a global expert survey and the analysis of evidence from **August 31, 2022, to September 1, 2024**, as well as secondary data drawn from other trusted sources to generate comprehensive metrics.

The Barometer provides:

- **Ratings not rankings** - As with the 1st Edition, indicators and scores remain on a 0-100 scale, where 100 reflects ‘best practices’ aligned with internationally agreed norms and frameworks. While comparisons between countries can highlight relative strengths and weaknesses, the primary value of the Barometer lies in identifying specific areas for improvement within each country.
- **Indicators and evidence** - Each primary indicator is structured around multiple sub-questions and supported by qualitative evidence that contextualizes the data, providing a deeper understanding of national data ecosystems.
- **A research network** - Research has been carried out through multiple regional hubs and in-country researchers. All findings have then been cross-checked with a group of external reviewers and a network of global thematic expert organizations. This model contributes to global capacity

building, creating a community of researchers and practitioners engaged in the exploration of data for the public good.

- **Actionable insights** - primary indicators have been designed to measure progress on data governance, core capabilities, and data availability that governments can improve upon over time with the support of civil society organizations playing a key role in influencing change.
- **Open data** - All scores and supporting evidence are published as open data, enabling further research, analysis, and reuse.

The report begins by evaluating foundational elements, Data Governance Foundations and Critical Competencies, which examine the legal, institutional, and human capacities necessary for building effective and responsible data systems. Building on this base evaluation, the Barometer then goes deeper to examine the availability and governance of data across key thematic sectors, including Public Finance, Procurement, Land Management, and Political Integrity, where data plays a vital role in advancing public interests.

The Barometer also explores cross-cutting themes, such as Data Foundations for AI, Inclusion, and Use of Data, recognizing that these dimensions are currently shaping how data operates across all sectors. Finally, regional snapshots of Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC) and Africa, developed by the regional hubs, reveal key trends, divergences, and contextual nuances that inform both local and global conversations. Combined, all elements of the Barometer's analysis offer a blueprint to help understand where progress is being made, where critical gaps persist, and what steps are needed to build healthier, more equitable data ecosystems.

| Key findings

Key Findings

Data Governance Frameworks Lagging in Implementation - Governance frameworks are crucial for making data both available and usable. However, the presence of regulatory frameworks alone does not guarantee effective implementation. The Barometer confirms a positive correlation between governance and data availability, but it also reveals a significant implementation gap, particularly in countries with weaker competencies.

Data Skills and Competencies are Essential - Without foundational digital infrastructure, skilled public officials, and robust institutions, even well-designed governance frameworks remain aspirational. Advanced data skills (e.g. AI, data analysis) and sustained training efforts are lacking in both regions.

AI Readiness Remains Fragmented and Underdeveloped - While AI is increasingly part of national development strategies, most data governance frameworks still lack explicit guidance on the use of data for AI development. Few training programs address AI ethics or algorithmic decision-making, and data-sharing frameworks rarely integrate AI-specific concerns. This underscores the urgent need to embed AI governance into broader data strategies.

Open Data Is at a Crossroads - Governments have made progress in adopting open data policies, but active, government-led initiatives are largely in decline. Many countries have open data frameworks in place which are falling short in terms of technical implementation, capacity-building, and sustained support. This threatens the sustainability and impact of open data programs.

Gaps in Transparency Undermine Accountability Goals - Thematic clusters reveal widespread gaps in transparency and interoperability. For instance, lobbying registers are nearly absent, beneficial ownership data is rarely public, and political finance data is inconsistently published. Fragmented datasets prevent the effective tracking of money, power, and influence.

Inclusion in Data Governance Is Largely Symbolic - Commitments to inclusion (e.g. for persons with disabilities or linguistic minorities) are rarely translated into practice. Accessibility is not commonly treated as a legal obligation, and data is rarely published in indigenous or widely spoken non-official languages.

Lack of Interoperability Is a Major Structural Weakness - Very few countries show evidence of interoperable datasets across political integrity, procurement, and company data. Without common identifiers and standards, efforts to follow data trails across domains are hindered, weakening transparency and anti-corruption efforts.

Results for LAC Indicate Strong Institutional Capacity but Limited Cross-Agency Coordination - Findings for LAC generally indicate stronger institutional capacity and better-developed digital infrastructures, but many initiatives risk stagnation due to limited cross-agency coordination and declining government-led support.

Results for Africa indicate Significant Progress but Ongoing Challenges with Implementation - Africa demonstrates significant advancement on policy and regulatory frameworks, especially in data protection laws, but continues to face serious implementation challenges due to weak infrastructures, limited interoperability, and gaps in institutional capacity.

The image features several overlapping, semi-transparent geometric shapes in shades of teal and purple. These shapes are positioned on the left side of the page, creating a layered, abstract composition. The teal shapes are more prominent, while the purple shapes are layered behind them, adding depth to the design.

| Methodology

Methodology

The 2nd Edition of the Barometer is the result of extensive research and coordinated efforts to expand on the findings of the 1st Edition. A key strength of the Barometer is its capacity to serve as a learning tool, providing insights into each country's strengths and weaknesses across various domains. For example, it allows for a nuanced analysis of countries with strong data frameworks but limited capacity to use data effectively. This 2nd Edition provides an assessment of 43 countries across Africa and Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC). Barbados is the only country not previously included in the 1st Edition. The study period for evidence gathering for the 2nd Edition was from August 31, 2022, to September 1, 2024.

Methodological Changes

The methodology for the 2nd Edition of the Barometer introduces a more refined approach to assessing indicators. In the 1st Edition, researchers were asked to answer all three sub-question sections — existence, elements, and extent — even when evidence for the existence of data was lacking. This exploratory approach allowed for broader information gathering, but it often placed a significant burden on researchers. The 2nd Edition adopts a more conditional flow that tailors the evidence gathering process. Researchers now complete sub-questions only when initial criteria are met: if no evidence exists, they complete an existence summary and move on; if some evidence is found, they assess extent; and if the data or framework¹ is nationally representative, they proceed to complete all sub-questions. This change not only sharpens the results, it enhances the comparability of findings across countries.

Further improvements include the introduction of two new distinct fields, existence summaries and element summaries, that replace the single “justification” requirement from the 1st Edition. This helps to clarify expectations and supports technical improvements to the survey tool.

1 Frameworks are understood as a set of policies, rules, and/or legislation designed to regulate or standardize the management and use of information assets.

The structure of all responses has also been standardized: sub-questions now follow a 3-option format (No, Partially, Yes), except for Critical Competencies indicators, where a 4-option scale (No, Isolated, Some, Widespread) is used to capture greater nuance. Importantly, the 2nd Edition narrows its focus to practices with national or representative coverage, intentionally excluding isolated cases that do not reflect scalable or meaningful practices.

The Data Use pillar from the 1st Edition has been discontinued due to concerns about the robustness and comparability of its scores. Instead, data use is now approached as a cross-cutting area of analysis through a variety of sub-questions that highlight the intersection of use with a variety of areas. The 2nd Edition now centres around three key pillars, Governance, Capabilities, and Availability, to produce a more representative and actionable picture of national data ecosystems.

Survey structure in the 2nd edition

Structure explained in a hierarchy schema

Geographical Scope

The decision to shift the focus of the 2nd Edition of the Global Data Barometer from a global to a regional approach that focuses on LAC and Africa is a strategic response to the challenges and opportunities that exist in these regions. A regional approach allows for a more nuanced analysis of their respective data ecosystems and tailored recommendations to address region-specific needs effectively.

Both regions, as part of the Global Majority, face similar structural challenges, including unequal access to digital infrastructure, inconsistent capacities for data management, and distinct, and often challenging, socio-political contexts. However, they have also often demonstrated significant progress in advancing data governance, transparency, and data use for public good, allowing for a rich and valuable comparative analysis.

Focusing on LAC and Africa enables the Barometer to offer deeper and more actionable findings through a closer examination of data governance models, key obstacles, and opportunities for leveraging data to promote social equity and transparency. Within LAC, for example, Caribbean nations face unique challenges as Small Island Developing States yet still share many governance and data access issues with Latin America and Africa.

Both regions are also undergoing digital transformations at very differing paces. While governments and civil society have embraced digital tools for governance, current efforts are often constrained by limited resources, inadequate infrastructure, and regulatory gaps. By analyzing these dynamics, the Barometer can identify both the drivers of progress and the remaining barriers to building sustainable data ecosystems.

This new edition also prioritizes ‘national’ data practices, ensuring that findings reflect scalable and impactful initiatives rather than just fragmented efforts. By focusing on regional strengths and challenges, the Barometer aims to generate insights that enhance data governance, promote public-good data use, and safeguard democratic values.

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Both regions mentioned above can further be divided into sub-regions. These sub-regions, although not the main focus of geographical analysis of the report, are mentioned in specific parts of the document and the Barometer results database with the aim of identifying findings for countries that share geographical proximity.

Sub-regions include:

- Caribbean
- Central America
- South America
- Northern Africa
- Central Africa
- Southern Africa
- East Africa
- Western Africa

Geographical

scope

Sub-regions

Sub-regions

Central Africa	
Southern Africa	
East Africa	
Western Africa	

Structure

At the centre of the Barometer’s methodology are 27 primary² indicators

Cluster	Action Area
Governance Foundation	Data Protection
	Data Management
	Data Sharing
	Data Infrastructure
Critical Competencies	Data Literacy
	Data Reuse
Political Integrity	Political Finance
	Interest and Asset Declarations
	Lobbying
	Right to Access Information Performance
	Political Integrity Interoperability
Land Management	Land Tenure
	Land Use
Company Information	Beneficial Ownership of Companies
	Company Register
Public Procurement	Public Procurement
Public Finance	Budget and Spending
Equitable Access	Accessibility
	Language

2 The full list of primary indicators is available online at: <https://handbook.globaldatabarometer.org/2024/>

(from the expert survey) and 11 secondary indicators (from recognized international sources). Each primary indicator includes sub-questions that are applied to weighted scores (0-100 scale) and supporting questions to help generate qualitative data. All indicators are categorized under the three pillars (Governance, Capabilities, and Availability) and can also be organized into specific action areas (spotlight topics of interest) and clusters (groups of action areas).

Lastly, the 2nd Edition has introduced new cross-cutting themes, such as AI, Inclusion, and Use of Data. These draw on a mixture of individual sub-questions and supporting questions, often distributed across multiple indicators, to reassemble the indicator data in innovative ways to surface further insights on key issues.

Data Collection

To measure country performance, the Barometer employs an expert survey that was developed in partnership with leading experts in different fields in an open, participatory process, in order to ensure consistent and comparable evaluations across different countries. The survey for the 2nd Edition is a significant evolution from the 1st Edition to better examine data policies and practices and their implications for data governance.

The expert survey was completed by a global network of regional hubs and national researchers using Survey Solutions software. The data collection process was guided by a range of documents and research tools, including the [Methodology Document](#), the [Research Manual](#), the [Reviewers Manual](#), the [Survey Tool Manual](#), and the [Indicators Library](#). The Barometer also implemented a capacity development program for researchers with a complete set of training materials.

There were several different roles and responsibilities related to data collection: national researchers were responsible for completing the expert survey and resolving concerns raised during review; regional hubs were responsible for coordinating researchers and the initial data review; regional reviewers were responsible for conducting the second layer of review; thematic reviewers were responsible for conducting a topic-related review;

and the Barometer core team was responsible for overseeing and facilitating the entire data collection process, as well as conducting a final review.

Primary data has been enriched with secondary data from multiple sources, such as the United Nations E-Government Development Survey, the International Telecommunication Union ICT Indicator Catalogue, the Freedom House Freedom in the World Report, the World Economic Forum Executive Opinion Survey, the World Bank GovTech Maturity Index, the World Intellectual Property Organization Global Innovation Index 2024, the World Bank Statistical Performance Indicators, and Access Info and the Centre for Law and Democracy's Global Right to Information Rating.

Data Collection

Key features

Scoring and Calculation

The national score for each country has been calculated as a weighted sum of all primary and secondary indicators, measured on a 0-100 scale, where 100 represents best practices as defined by internationally agreed norms or frameworks.

The primary indicators at the core of the Barometer's methodology serve as the basis for three different types of scores:

- **National Score** - represents the overall performance of a country across all evaluated topics.
- **Cluster Score** - traces results across Governance, Capabilities, and Availability to support the analysis of key challenges and development areas, such as Governance Foundations, Critical Competencies, Public Finance, Public Procurement, Political Integrity, etc.
- **Action Area Score** - assesses essential elements of a healthy and functional data ecosystem, such as Data Protection, Data Sharing, Data Reuse, Data Literacy, etc. They are a group of indicators.

Each indicator is assigned a weighting based on its type. Primary indicators carry greater weight than secondary indicators, while non-thematic indicators (such as data-sharing frameworks or civil service training) are weighted slightly higher than thematic indicators (such as beneficial ownership frameworks or political finance data). The only exception to the primary indicators weighting system is the Language Coverage and Data indicator, which is non-weighted (excluded from scoring) due to limitations in the survey.

With regard to secondary indicators, those derived from index variables received a higher weight than single metrics from a secondary source. To ensure consistency, weights have been scaled so that national, cluster, and action area scores remain within the 0-100 range.

Each indicator's score is multiplied by its weight and the results are summarized. Unlike ranking-based methodologies, the Barometer functions as a rating instrument and does not apply min-max scaling. A country can only score 100 if all its input indicators also reach 100, meaning that the difference between a country's score and 100 reflects the gap between its current performance and the normative ideal set by the Barometer. However, the Barometer norms are not designed to be unattainable. If the highest observed scores for each indicator were combined for an idealized country, that country would achieve a score of 88.24, demonstrating that the Barometer's standards are fundamentally within reach. A full breakdown of the weighting system is available in the [Annex](#).

Core Areas of Analysis

Core Areas of Analysis

For the 2nd Edition of the Global Data Barometer, we have refined our approach by organizing indicators into structured clusters and action areas to ensure a comprehensive assessment of the foundations necessary for a healthy data ecosystem. These clusters and action areas provide a consistent lens for evaluating key aspects of data governance, capabilities, and availability.

Among these, the Governance Foundations and Critical Competencies clusters specifically highlight the essential frameworks and capacities needed for effective data production, storage, publication, and use. The Governance Foundations cluster includes several action areas, such as data protection, data management, and data sharing — fundamental components that support responsible data ecosystems. The Critical Competencies cluster focuses on the skills and practices required to leverage data effectively.

Each cluster is composed of action areas and interrelated indicators that work together to provide a multidimensional view of the state of data in each country. By structuring the analysis in this way, the Barometer aims to offer a more nuanced and actionable understanding of how different elements of the broader data ecosystem come together to advance data for the public good.

Governance Foundations

Summary

- Data protection laws have expanded as Africa has progressed significantly and Latin America is moving closer to universal adoption.
- AI governance depends on strong data governance, yet most frameworks fail to integrate AI-specific considerations into their data protection regulations, posing significant risks.
- Data management has improved with notable increases in quality control processes, user feedback mechanisms, and metadata standards.
- Latin America leads on data management with Brazil and Chile indicating strong digital governance and Africa still exhibiting stark regional disparities.
- Data-sharing frameworks have grown with Africa leading in private-sector data sharing, but frameworks still lack specific references to the AI-specific requirements.
- Africa regulations often include restrictions on data brokers, reflecting different regulatory priorities.

The Foundational Role of Data Governance

Data has become an invaluable asset used to shape decisions and drive innovation across critical domains. When effectively governed, data fuels progress and enables more inclusive, evidence-based policymaking; however, working to realize the full potential of data for the public good presents many challenges, including privacy risks, inequitable access, and regulatory gaps. These risks underscore the need for robust data governance mechanisms

that balance innovation with the protection of fundamental rights.

Governments play a central role in shaping this landscape by establishing regulations, setting international standards, and ensuring oversight. Effective data governance, especially for government-held data, not only enhances accessibility but also fosters trust and safeguards privacy. Despite the growing focus on artificial intelligence (AI), the foundational importance of data governance for AI development remains underappreciated. As [Stefaan Verhulst and Friederike Schüür](#) (2023) emphasized, robust data governance frameworks are essential for sound AI governance. Neglecting this connection risks fragmented policies and missed opportunities for cooperation.

Weak data governance not only undermines AI systems, it also threatens broader data integrity, regulatory compliance, and public trust. The [2021 World Development Report](#) has affirmed that unlocking the full potential of data for development requires comprehensive national data systems underpinned by strong governance frameworks that address data quality, technical standards, and transparency. More recently, the [Global Digital Compact](#) (2024) reiterated this need, warning that the rapid expansion in data collection and sharing, if unaccompanied by privacy safeguards, could deepen inequalities and erode human rights.

Progress and Regional Differences in Data Protection

The 2nd Edition of the Global Data Barometer highlights notable progress in data protection across LAC and Africa. Improvements in legal frameworks have strengthened safeguards for data rights, especially in emerging areas, such as algorithmic decision-making and location-related data.

Some countries stand out for their robust frameworks and strong enforcement, including South Africa³, Botswana, and Brazil; however, progress in general is uneven. Many countries still lack comprehensive data protection laws, and others face challenges in enforcement or scope. In particular, Central America and West Africa show slower advancement with countries like Paraguay⁴ and Honduras⁵ still working to strengthen their frameworks.

In countries with regulations in place, several positive trends are emerging:

- Coverage of access and correction rights has improved (+11.43).
- Attention to algorithmic privacy has grown significantly (+29.04).
- Mechanisms to address rights violations have expanded (+10.96), often with independent oversight.

3 And the establishment in 2022 of the Enforcement Committee, in terms of section 50 of the Protection of Personal Information Act No 4 of 2013 (POPIA).

4 Personal Credit Data Protection Law.

5 Law of the Civil Registry and the Law for Transparency and for Access to Public Information.

Key Elements of Data Protection Regulatory Frameworks: 1st vs 2nd Edition Comparison

Barometer findings indicate that Africa, in particular, has made notable progress with many laws now in place that align with the African Union’s Malabo Convention which has now been ratified by 15 member states. Still, some legal frameworks remain limited in scope, having been developed to support digitization without comprehensive safeguards. Latin America’s development has been slower but more widespread. While several countries still lack comprehensive legislation, the region has long-standing legal precedents influenced by the EU’s data protection directives and, more recently, the GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation).

These regional advances illustrate a growing global recognition of data protection as central to building trustworthy digital societies. Overall, the 2nd Edition of the Barometer indicates a global trend toward stronger and more

comprehensive data protection frameworks to address emerging challenges like algorithmic decision-making and group privacy, but disparities remain that point to the importance of implementation beyond just the creation of new legislation.

Progress and Regional Differences in Data Protection

Effective data protection frameworks must be complemented by sound data management practices to ensure data quality, usability, and security throughout the data lifecycle. Data management forms the operational core of a healthy data ecosystem, translating governance principles into practice.

Data management frameworks should provide a foundation for sustainable and responsible data handling. These include quality control, interoperability requirements, metadata standards, and mechanisms for updating and archiving. Increasingly, governments are also integrating user feedback into management practices, recognizing the importance of usability alongside accessibility.

The 2nd Edition indicates improvements in data management across both regions, particularly in documentation, metadata, feedback mechanisms, and technical standards:

- Quality control processes nearly doubled (+23.81).
- Feedback systems indicate the highest gains (+26.66).
- Adoption of metadata standards (+19.53).
- Adoption of structured technical standards (+21.43).

Key Features of Data Management Regulatory Frameworks: 1st vs 2nd Edition Comparison

In South America, Chile and Brazil demonstrate high data management capabilities, reflecting the existence of strong digital government frameworks and digital public infrastructure, while the Caribbean and Central America reflect ongoing disparity among countries. In Africa, data management scores are generally lower with Western and Middle Africa underperforming. Eastern Africa presents a mix, while Northern Africa also includes lower scores. Southern Africa has the widest range of results among countries in the region with South Africa clearly the regional leader.

As countries develop more structured and transparent data management systems, they lay the groundwork for interoperable, user-centred, and rights-respecting data ecosystems.

The Growing Recognition of Data Sharing Frameworks

Effective data sharing is the next layer in the data governance stack to enable collaboration across sectors while safeguarding privacy and ethics. Governments, civil society, and the private sector all manage valuable data, and structured frameworks are essential for facilitating responsible exchange practices.

Data sharing involves granting specific stakeholders access to data while implementing defined use limitations and control mechanisms. Various regulatory frameworks facilitate responsible access to sensitive, proprietary, or non-open data use, ranging from legally binding regulations and policies to more flexible guidance documents. The establishment of clear frameworks for data sharing is essential to ensure security, accountability, and the ethical/responsible use of data. Without standardized data-sharing protocols and regulations, the risks of misuse, privacy breaches, and other unintended consequences increase significantly.

The 2nd Edition observes a shift toward more regulatory frameworks for data sharing. In the 1st Edition, just over half of all countries assessed (52.38%) had data sharing frameworks in place. Today, nearly three-quarters of countries (74.42%) have working frameworks, including regulations and/or interoperability guidelines.

Data sharing and data protection regulatory frameworks, though distinct, often intersect, especially when it comes to handling personal data. Researchers assessing data-sharing indicators for the Barometer frequently reference multiple data protection frameworks as well as interoperability frameworks: analysis reveals that six countries refer to three different types of frameworks to address data-sharing concerns, and 15 countries refer to two.

Regional differences are also evident in the make-up of data sharing frameworks. In Africa, data protection frameworks play a more prominent role with 13 of 16 valid responses incorporating them. In contrast, Latin American countries tend to prioritize interoperability frameworks with 14 of 16 countries

relying on them to support data-sharing governance. These regional variations underscore that a diverse range of approaches are being taken to regulate and facilitate data sharing across policy environments.

Additional policy and regulatory frameworks, such as right to information (RTI) frameworks, also serve as mechanisms for enabling data sharing. Researchers from someWn which data-sharing policies are being shaped globally.

Data Sharing Types in LAC and Africa: Comparing GDB 1st and 2nd Editions

Despite the progress to date, AI-related considerations remain largely underdeveloped in most data sharing frameworks implemented as of yet. As AI systems evolve to increasingly rely on large-scale multi-data access, the need for integrating AI-specific guidelines into data sharing frameworks becomes more urgent.

Countries in both Africa and LAC are increasingly embedding accountability and oversight mechanisms into their frameworks that assign responsibilities and ensure monitoring practices. Notably, Africa has adopted much stronger regulation of data brokers and placed limits on data commercialization, a trend less prevalent in Latin America.

Together, these developments signal an evolving global architecture for data sharing – one that must now adapt to the new risks and demands of AI, cross-border flows, and the ethical use of sensitive data.

Observations

Strengthening data governance is essential not only for safeguarding personal information but also for fostering the development of responsible artificial intelligence (AI), promoting ethical data sharing, and rebuilding public trust in digital systems. In an era where data underpins nearly every aspect of social and economic life, robust governance frameworks are no longer optional. They are critical to ensuring that digital innovation aligns with democratic values and public interests.

To advance this vision, countries must:

- Take deliberate steps to integrate data governance principles into their AI strategies, ensuring that systems are fair, transparent, and accountable.
- Address legislative gaps in data protection with stronger enforcement mechanisms and independent oversight bodies to ensure that regulations are effectively implemented.
- Invest in national data management capacities, including user feedback systems, standardized metadata, and interoperable technical standards, are equally crucial.

Additionally, comprehensive and enforceable data-sharing frameworks must be developed with AI-specific provisions and clear lines of accountability. Ultimately, data governance is not just a technical necessity; it is the foundation upon which inclusive digital development and rights-respecting AI must be built.

Critical Competencies

Summary

- **Data Capabilities and Infrastructure Disparities** – LAC generally has stronger foundational data infrastructures than Africa as a result of dedicated government bodies responsible for data governance or management, as well as higher levels of internet access and digital government capabilities.
- **Digital Government Gaps** – LAC countries like Brazil demonstrate advanced digital government capabilities, while many other nations, particularly in Africa, still face challenges in integrating digital platforms for public services and data dissemination.
- **Data Literacy** – Structured training programs for public officials are essential for strengthening data capabilities, but many countries lack consistent or well-funded efforts to build data literacy within the public sector.
- **Challenges in Data Reuse** – Approximately 63% of countries have open data initiatives, but only 46.51% are government-led and most reflect limited success in sustaining these initiatives. Government support for open data reuse is uneven. In some countries support is generally provided through events and hackathons, while in many others there is limited government involvement.

It is essential to examine the enabling environment that allows effective data governance to be translated into meaningful public impact. Data infrastructure—the skills, institutions, and capacities that support the effective use of data—form the bedrock upon which data governance mechanisms can be successfully implemented. Without this foundation, even the best-designed governance frameworks may remain mostly conceptual. In the

Barometer, these broader conditions are examined under Critical Competencies which looks at the capacities needed not only to access and process data, but to put it to use in ways that advance the public good. This section analyzes and compares the current state of data capabilities in Africa and LAC, drawing on both primary indicators and secondary sources. The focus is on the conditions that enable data to be collected, managed, shared, and used to serve the public good, including access to key infrastructure elements like internet connectivity, the availability of digital public infrastructure, the strength of institutions, and the presence of an informed and skilled civil service.

Data Infrastructure

Before examining the primary indicators within the Critical Competencies cluster, it is important to recognize that a broader set of data capabilities, spanning infrastructure, institutions, and skills, provide the essential context for understanding the foundations of an effective data system. These capabilities, assessed with the support of secondary sources, help illuminate persistent regional disparities in the enabling environment for data use.

Institutional capacity remains a key differentiator. Countries such as Argentina, Brazil, Ecuador, Peru, and Uruguay perform strongly on the WBG GovTech Maturity Index⁶, reflecting well-established institutional arrangements for managing data. In contrast, countries like Cameroon, Gambia, and Liberia score very low or even zero, highlighting significant governance and implementation gaps.

Internet connectivity⁷, a prerequisite for data access and digital inclusion, also reveals stark contrasts. While Chile and the Bahamas demonstrate high levels of access, countries such as Uganda and Liberia face major infrastructure barriers. Morocco, with over 90 percent penetration, offers a compelling example of how a concerted strategic investment can bridge the gap.

6 [WBG GovTech Maturity Index \(GTMI\)](#).

7 UTI: fixed broadband basket and individuals using the internet.

Finally, digital government and interoperability capabilities often mirror a similar divide. Brazil scores 90.63 for government online services and 100 in digital government, showcasing a highly advanced digital ecosystem, while the results for African countries tend toward a more mixed picture. Angola, for example, scored 39.62 and 50 respectively on these indicators, while South Africa presents a brighter example with scores of 88.72 and 83.33. These differences suggest that while some African countries are advancing, others lag due to more limited investment in infrastructure, policy coordination, or institutional readiness.

These disparities constrain the extent to which governments can embed data into public service delivery and decision-making or address social inequities. Addressing these gaps in the Critical Competencies cluster is essential, in particular, the need to advance robust policies and initiatives for data reuse and a civil service equipped to apply data for the public good. Strengthening digital public infrastructure (DPI⁸) remains a key area for strategic investment to ensure governments can fully utilize data in governance processes.

Data Literacy

Within the Critical Competencies cluster, a critical area examined by the Barometer are the data skills and literacy levels of public officials. Training civil servants to manage and use data effectively is fundamental to embedding data practices across government operations. The Barometer's data literacy indicator reveals considerable variation in how countries approach this challenge with differing levels of investment and institutional commitment to training public sector personnel.

LAC countries, such as Brazil, Colombia, and the Dominican Republic, stand out for their training programs, particularly in critical areas like data protection. Yet, across both LAC and Africa, technical skills training in data analysis and publication is not prioritized.

8 https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/digital-public-infrastructure-for-digital-governments_ff525dc8-en.html

Training Availability for Technical and Non-Technical Public Officials

Moreover, training often targets non-technical personnel, potentially neglecting the personnel most responsible for data management. The lack of focus on emerging areas of data application is also concerning as training on AI is rarely offered, posing a significant risk as governments without foundational knowledge and skills in AI may struggle to regulate it or deploy it responsibly.

Focus Areas of Training: What Topics Are Being Covered?

Governments must invest in the institutional, technical, and human capacities that enable meaningful data reuse, alongside strong regulatory frameworks. Without these foundational elements, the promise of public data, particularly open data, will remain largely unfulfilled. To realize its full potential as a catalyst for innovation, accountability, and inclusive development in the digital age, open data must be underpinned by coherent strategies, capable institutions, and a skilled public sector, as explored in the following subsection.

Data Reuse

In today's AI-dominated era, open data policies and initiatives are no longer simply tools for transparency, they are foundational and necessary elements of digital and data governance. Open data initiatives work to underpin government support for innovation, to empower civil society, and to help shape responsible AI development.

The strength of these ecosystems is evaluated by the Barometer through the Data Reuse Cluster across three interconnected action areas: Open Data Policy, Open Data Initiatives, and Government Support for Reuse. Governments use a combination of these components to form the system through which data can become a shared asset that is available, usable, and leveraged for decision-making, innovation, and accountability. Yet, despite growing recognition of the importance of open data, this edition of the Barometer reveals signs of stagnation and uneven progress in government-led initiatives.

The 2nd Edition of the Barometer indicates that 63% of the countries assessed have some form of open data initiative; however, the proportion of active, government-led initiatives has declined to 46.51%, down from 52.38% in the 1st Edition. Notably, six initiatives in Africa are non-government-led, one of which is now inactive, reflecting persistent challenges in institutionalizing open data programs. Findings suggest that while open data remains on the agenda in many countries, a lack of sustained government commitment is limiting the effectiveness of reuse initiatives. Furthermore, broader government-wide engagement is only present in 14 countries, while in others, such as Rwanda, Senegal, and Trinidad and Tobago, there is very limited institutional involvement.

Status of Open Data Initiatives: Comparison Between 1st and 2nd Editions

These disparities underscore the need to move beyond policy formulation and toward sustained institutional and financial support for open data. Government support plays a pivotal role in sustaining these programs; however, the Barometer finds that just over half of the assessed countries provide meaningful support for reuse, often only through events like hackathons or communication strategies, while direct financial support remains rare.

Regional disparities are also clearly visible. Some countries are more likely to benefit from government support as seen in [Uruguay's Datacamp](#), whereas many other countries lack visible mechanisms to promote reuse. Even in countries, such as Nigeria, where data governance scores are relatively high, structured programs to foster data reuse are absent, pointing to a continuing gap between policy development and practical implementation.

Key Features of Open Data Initiatives

Beyond institutional engagement, the robustness of open data ecosystems is also shaped by the quality of open data policies, specifically with regard to how well they define, regulate, and enable data reuse. The Barometer evaluates these policies across five key elements, revealing varying degrees of implementation across both regions. While there is generally an alignment with open data principles, specifically the definition of open data, open licensing, and machine-readability, significant regional differences emerge in the more technical and institutional aspects, such as in the use of data standards and capacity-building.

Among the five elements examined, alignment is greatest with regard to the definition of open data (81.82 responded “Yes” or “Partially”). This suggests that in most of the countries where a framework exists, there is a clear attempt to specifically articulate what open data means. Similarly, adherence to open licensing and machine-readability principles is strong with 72.73% and 68.18% responding “Yes” respectively, indicating a broad consensus on ensuring that open data is reusable and provided in accessible formats.

Key Features required by Open Data Policies

In contrast, there are major inconsistencies in the use of data standards with only 31.82% of countries responding “Yes”. This points to a significant area of divergence, where even among countries with open data frameworks, the adoption of standardized data structures remains inconsistent or entirely absent. The relatively high number of “No” responses highlights the fact that standards are often omitted altogether, possibly reflecting regional disparities in technical capacity or policy maturity. Similarly, the evidence of capacity-building for government officials remains uneven. While 59.09% of countries were positive overall, six of 18 valid responses indicated a complete lack of attention to this issue, underscoring that where legal and technical elements are being addressed to some degree, the human and institutional capacity to implement open data policies is still frequently neglected.

The decline of government-led initiatives combined with weak institutional support poses a serious threat to the long-term sustainability of open data initiatives. For example, Costa Rica’s once-active open data initiative is no longer operational. Without committed leadership, dedicated funding, and enterprise-wide alignment across agencies, open data efforts risk stagnating or collapsing. At the same time, inconsistencies in the participation of government agencies demonstrate that political will and coordinated action can significantly influence the impact of open data.

Finally, the Barometer finds that support for data reuse continues to vary widely across user groups with civil society organizations and academia often receiving the most attention, while private sector users remain comparatively

underserved or unrecorded. This uneven approach may limit the broader economic potential of open data, particularly in low-and middle-income contexts, where private innovation plays a critical role in development. Moving forward, governments will need to adopt more holistic strategies that integrate legal, technical, and institutional dimensions of open data governance, while proactively supporting diverse user communities to realize the full promise of open data as a public good.

Government Support for Different Types of Data Users

The findings from the Data Reuse Cluster highlights that we have come to a critical inflection point for open data. While many countries have laid the groundwork through policies and initiatives, the lack of sustained support, cross-agency coordination, and attention to user needs, is limiting or blocking continuing progress. To fully unlock the value of open data, governments must move beyond foundational commitments and invest in data governance and the institutional, technical, and human capacities that make data truly reusable. Only then will open data meet its potential as a driver of innovation, accountability, and inclusive development in the digital age.

Observations

The comparative analysis of Critical Competencies clusters underscores once again that LAC, particularly South America, currently possesses stronger foundational data capabilities. These strengths include more established institutions, broader internet access, more developed digital government services, and more consistent training efforts. However, gaps still remain in both regions-especially with regard to civil service training, advanced technical skills, and equitable access to infrastructure.

For African countries, the results highlight the urgent need to invest in institutions, connectivity, and human capital. For LAC, the priority may lie in deepening digital maturity, fostering interoperability, and preparing for emerging challenges such as the responsible integration of AI into evolving data governance practices. Bridging these gaps is not only about improving technical infrastructure, it is ultimately about enabling inclusive, effective, and rights-respecting data use for the public good.

To address these gaps and improve overall data ecosystems, it is essential to strengthen institutional capacity. Specifically, countries with weak or fragmented data structures should consider:

- Establishing dedicated national data institutions responsible for overseeing government-wide data management. Integrating data governance into broader national digital strategies will ensure a more coordinated and sustainable approach, as well as foster coherence across government agencies.
- Expanding internet access is critical to enabling broader data utilization, particularly in countries with low connectivity. Governments should prioritize investments in digital infrastructure to ensure equitable access to data, particularly in remote and underserved areas.
- Developing national digital government strategies that integrate open data, interoperability, and DPI can significantly strengthen public service delivery.

- Civil service training must be expanded to equip public officials with the necessary data skills. Structured training programs should be implemented to enhance both technical and non-technical personnel's capacity to work with data effectively. AI and advanced analytics should be incorporated into training curricula to ensure that governments are prepared for emerging data challenges. Establishing regional training hubs or online learning platforms can provide scalable, cost-effective solutions to improve data literacy and technical capacity.

Thematic Areas of Analysis

Availability

Summary

- Thematic clusters offer sector-specific insights on how data is governed, shared, and used across critical public domains with a focus on accountability, equity, and institutional integrity.
- Legal frameworks for public finance and procurement exist in most countries, but they often fail to require the publication of structured, open, and machine-readable data, which limits their usefulness for accountability efforts.
- In nearly every cluster, data is more likely to be available than truly open. Many countries release some information, but few meet core open data standards such as bulk download, machine-readability, or open licensing.
- Political integrity data reveals the most significant gaps. Lobbying registers are rare, and interoperability between datasets like asset declarations, political finance, and company information is almost entirely absent.
- In the area of political finance, while most countries have some legal requirements in place, less than half actually publish the data. Disclosures on donor identities, in-kind contributions, and third-party spending are particularly limited.
- Beneficial ownership transparency is especially weak. Although the majority of countries collect this data, only a few make it publicly accessible in a usable format.
- Land tenure and land use data are often fragmented or partial. National coverage is rare, and data related to indigenous or communal rights is missing in a large share of countries.
- Procurement data is more widely published than other clusters, but critical information on the implementation phase of contracts is still lacking in most cases.
- RTI performance data is somewhat more consistently available, yet many countries still do not report on appeals processes, withheld materials, or performance by agency.

In addition to the core areas of analysis, Governance Foundations and Critical Competencies, the 2nd Edition of the Global Data Barometer includes a set of thematic clusters developed in collaboration with subject matter experts that examine the availability of specific sector data and the advancement of governance over that data. Their insights have been instrumental in updating and improving each thematic area, ensuring that our assessments remain relevant, comprehensive, and reflective of evolving challenges in data ecosystems.

The function of these clusters is to explore the availability of data used to address long-standing issues related to accountability, power, and money. By structuring the analysis around these thematic areas, the Barometer provides a more nuanced perspective on how data is being used (or misused) in key governance and economic domains.

The Political Integrity cluster examines transparency and accountability mechanisms essential for democratic governance, covering several action areas, such as political finance, RTI performance, interest and asset declaration, and lobbying. The Land Management cluster focuses on land tenure and land use, emphasizing the critical need for high-quality, accessible data on land ownership and utilization. The Company Information cluster investigates the transparency of business operations, particularly through an assessment of company registers and efforts made to determine beneficial ownership. Finally, the Public Procurement and Public Finance clusters scrutinize government spending and procurement processes, assessing the availability of data for enabling accountability and public oversight of budgets, expenditures, and contracting practices.

By structuring these clusters around key accountability and policy concerns, and by strengthening our collaboration with expert organizations, the Barometer aims to shed light on the role of data in strengthening institutional integrity, reducing corruption, and fostering equitable access to information. The resulting insights not only inform policy reforms but also empower advocates, researchers, and decision-makers working to enhance data-driven accountability in the different regions.

Political Integrity

The Political Integrity cluster explores how data is being harnessed to protect and promote fairness, transparency, and accountability in public life. It focuses on critical action areas such as political finance, RTI, lobbying, and interest and asset declarations, all cornerstones for ensuring that political systems serve the public good and not private or hidden interests.

When information about who influences political decisions, how money flows through campaigns, or what interests public officials hold is made accessible, citizens are better equipped to hold those in power to account. Transparent, participatory governance requires not only laws and institutions, but also high-quality, open data that reveals the inner workings of political systems. This includes shedding light on lobbying practices, enabling the scrutiny of campaign donations, and supporting informed public engagement through strong RTI frameworks.

In societies where political integrity is prioritized and made visible through data, trust in institutions can grow, democratic processes can deepen, and decisions are more likely to reflect the needs of all, not just the powerful few.

Political Finance

With regard to political finances, the Barometer examines the legal and regulatory frameworks that require political parties and political campaigns to disclose information about how they raise and spend money. It also examines whether the available data provides a comprehensive overview of the financial state of political parties and political campaigns, including their income, assets, and liabilities, as well as other ways of raising money, and how the money is spent.

Overall results indicate that the frameworks in place are achieving some level of progress in 39 of the 43 countries assessed; however, this progress is unequal across countries across the two regions. The average score in LAC was 65.59 and, in Africa, 42.48. In both regions, political finances data is required to be collected in 91% of the countries but is only required to be published in 70% of the countries under their existing frameworks. Barometer results indicate that only 42% of the 43 countries studied have made this data

available directly from the government.

A deeper examination of the 39 countries with a legal framework in place reveals that 85% of them are required by law to publish information on party income and spending, that 69% require the publication of information on financial contributions, and 62% require the publication of information on in-kind and nonfinancial support. However, these legal frameworks still show weaknesses on the definitions of campaigning for third parties with 74% do not define third party participation at all, and 46% do not define campaigning for candidates, nor requiring donors' identities to be made public (41%).

Key Components of Public Finance Regulatory Frameworks

Of the countries that publish some political finance data (18 of 43), all of them make available some data on financial contributions, and 89% of them make available some data on the income and spending of parties or candidates. However, 78% of the countries with data available do not offer financial details on third parties, and 56% do not offer data on the assets and liabilities of parties or candidates.

What Public Finance Data is Available?

In terms of open data, results indicate positive adherence to the principle of releasing the data free of charge (all countries offer the data free or partially free), the principle of timely and updated data (94% of countries fully or partially comply), and to releasing historical data (78% of the countries fully or partially comply). However, there is minimal adherence to other key principles, such as the use of open licences (not met by 83% of countries), making data available as a whole (not met by 78% of countries), and making data available in machine readable formats (not met by 61% of countries).

Good examples of effective platforms for political finance data can be found in Brazil and Peru. In Brazil, there are [websites](#) run by the Superior Electoral Court that contain data on political finance, downloadable for free and in open formats. The data is updated and allows for the exploration of specific information, such as donations made by individuals. In Peru, the [“Claridad”](#) political financing platform provides access to searchable information on private, public, and indirect financing that allows data to be downloaded in assets, machine readable formats and provides reports on income, expenditures, liabilities, and in-kind donations.

A total of 48 African states are bound to adopt measures to incorporate the practice of transparency into political finance as they have signed to the [African Union Convention on Preventing and Combatting Corruption](#) and the United Nations Convention Against Corruption. Political parties, legislators, and oversight officials in Africa must take a hard look in the GDB mirror and give citizens what they deserve: some clarity about political financing.

Jorge Valladares, Transparency International

Interest and Asset Declarations

Countries normally require public officials to declare their interests and assets in order to avoid conflicts of interest and illicit enrichment. The Barometer evaluates the strengths of legal or regulatory frameworks in this area that direct how related data is made available to the general public.

General findings of the Barometer related to country frameworks that require interest and asset declaration indicate a very uneven situation regionally as the LAC countries scored an average of 69.95 points and African countries scored much less with an average of 47.37 points. Interestingly, in both regions, this data is required to be collected by 100% of the countries that have a legal framework (42 of 43) but is only required to be published by 49% of the countries, presenting a significant gap between collection and publication activities.

Although 49% of countries (22 of the 42) require this data to be published, only 12 really publish any data through government action (2 have this data available but not as result of government action), illustrating further limitations in terms of compliance with data publication.

A deeper analysis of relevant frameworks indicates positive developments in a few key areas: 95% of countries are required to collect information on interests, assets, and liabilities; and 67% are required to collect information on interests, assets, and liabilities held by a public official's spouse, family members, or other close associates. However, 40% of countries still do not require the collection of specific information on non financial interests, and 30% do not require the collection of information on significant changes in interests, assets, and liabilities.

Key Components of Regulatory Frameworks for Interest and Asset Declarations

In terms of data availability, as stated above, only 14 of 43 countries publish any data related to interest and asset declarations. The majority of published information is on interests, assets, and liabilities, with 71% of the countries publishing to some degree. However, 79% of countries do not offer information related to significant changes in interest, assets, and liabilities or information related to interests, assets and liabilities held by a public official’s spouse, family members, or other close associates.

Data Elements for Interest and Asset Declarations

Notably, countries that do publish information still have difficulty adhering to key open data principles: 71% of them do not make the data available as a whole, and 62% do not make it available under an open license or in machine readable formats. However, 93% of countries do offer the data free of charge, 86% provide updated data, and 71% have historical data available.

Interesting examples related to making data available on interest and asset declarations can be found in Brazil and Chile. In Brazil, the available [data](#) contains unique identifiers for each public official, disclosing payroll and travel data; data is timely, free of charge, openly licensed, and can be downloaded through an [API](#). In Chile, the [InfoProbidad](#) website provides open data on declarations of interests and assets of Chilean public officials, including details about their assets, investments, debts, and potential conflicts of interest, and the website offers search tools that allow any citizen to access the information quickly.

Lobbying Registers

The Barometer evaluates the implementation of legal and regulatory frameworks that govern lobbying data, typically in the form of lobbying registers, and whether the data from these registers is available to the public. The Barometer's examination aligns with international definitions of lobbying: any direct or indirect communication with a public official that is made, managed, or directed with the purpose of influencing public decision-making.

The existence or implementation of frameworks related to lobbying received the lowest scores by the Barometer among all evaluated frameworks. The average score of the Latin American countries was only 9.21, and the average score of the African countries was 0 (in both cases out of 100). The only countries that have some level of framework implementation are Chile, Colombia, and Mexico. Brazil and Costa Rica have drafted a framework, but they have not yet made it official. Beyond these countries, no other studied country has a legal framework to support oversight of lobbying.

Results of the 5 countries with some level of progress on lobbying frameworks indicates that all of them provide key definitions on lobbyists, lobbying clients, lobbying activities, and public officials, as well as on the collection and publication of the identities of lobbyists, lobbyist clients, and

public officials who engage with lobbyists. However, none of these definitions cover the collection and publication of lobbyist goals, and 80% of them do not cover the collection and publication of data on lobbying events.

In terms of data availability, only three countries have made data available to the public as a direct result of government action: Chile, Colombia, and Mexico. Findings related to these countries reveals a very positive situation in Chile, where a range of data is made available (see below). However, only two data types were somehow present across all three countries: unique identifiers for lobbyists and public officials and the clear identification of lobbying clients.

Availability of Different Types of Lobbying Data

The only open data principle adhered to by all three countries was making data available free-of-charge. Principles related to timely, updated, and machine-readable data were met by two of the countries.

The Chilean Infobby Portal is a good example of how lobbying data can be made available. The data on the portal is updated every month and contains unique identifiers for each lobbyist and public official by RUT (unique tax registration) and is made available under a Creative Commons 4.0 license. The portal also features a search function that enables users to find specific information efficiently, including data visualization tools.

Right to Information

Most countries around the world have provisions by which members of the public can request information that is held by the government. The Barometer examines the transparency of a country's right to information processes as defined by legal and regulatory frameworks that govern the release of RTI performance data.

General results illustrate important differences in terms of regional performance and the legal frameworks that govern RTI performance data. Latin American countries scored an average of 58.40, while African countries scored an average of 27.59. Both regions show significant room for improvement.

In both regions, RTI performance data is required to be collected by 70% of the countries (that is 30 out of the 43), while only 49% of them (that is 21 out of the 43) make the publication of this data mandatory. Results from data availability show a good level of compliance with this last mandate as 42% of the countries (that is 18 out of the 43) are publishing RTI performance data.

A deeper analysis of the 30 frameworks in place reveals that 83% of those countries explicitly require RTI performance data to be linked to each individual government department or agency; 87% of countries fully or partially require data on the number of information requests submitted and processed; 73% of countries fully or partially require information on the material withheld and the reasons for withholding it. A main limitation of most frameworks is that they do not require the release of information on service performance metrics (e.g. only 43% of countries require information on the time taken to respond to requests for information).

Data Collection Requirements in RTI Frameworks

In terms of data availability, among the 18 countries with RTI data, 94% of them have data on the number of information requests submitted and processed, and 83% of them provide a link to each specific agency. However, 61% of them do not offer any data related to RTI appeals nor describe the material withheld and the reasons for withholding it.

Types of Data Available on RTI Framework Performance

The adherence to open data principles for RTI data reveals both strengths and weaknesses. On the positive side, 100% of the countries that provide data offer the data free of charge. 89% have updated data, 83% have historical data, and 67% have data in machine readable formats. On the negative side, 61% of countries do not make the data available as a whole, and 50% of them do not release it under an open license or offer alternative tools for data exploration.

An illustrative example of RTI performance data accessibility can be found in Brazil, where a [government portal](#) has published requests and responses since 2015. In addition, an interactive and user-friendly [panel](#) provides detailed, up-to-date data on the implementation and performance of the RTI law, all in open formats that can be easily downloaded and reused.

Access to higher-quality, up-to-date political integrity data is essential for understanding which policies to advance. To make this happen, an important next step for countries is to strengthen partnerships. Data disclosure alone is not enough for political integrity data to achieve impact. Networks of people and institutions working together are needed, such as the media, oversight bodies, the private sector, and civil society organizations.

Partnerships are critical for several reasons. First, engaging a variety of stakeholders helps to overcome vested interests, which often pose obstacles in this area. Building coalitions of reformers also helps to ensure sustainability and lasting change. As more people become invested in reforms, it becomes more difficult to undo initiatives as a result of political transitions or new stronger opposition. The Open Government Partnership (OGP) is one example of a platform through which reformers can advance these initiatives.

Renzo Falla Lopez-Open Government Partnership

Political Integrity Interoperability

The Barometer examines the interoperability of key political integrity datasets, both at the basic level of detailed documentation and with regard to the consistency of formats, standards, data fields, and identifiers. The evaluation examines the interoperability of all four political integrity datasets (Political Finance, Interest and Asset disclosure, Lobbying, and RTI), as well as the other thematic datasets (Company Information, Public Finance, and Procurement).

The Barometer findings indicate that only 7% of the studied countries have achieved some level of interoperability, while a further 5% exhibit some isolated evidence of interoperability. The remaining 88% of countries indicate a lack of data interoperability across political integrity and thematic datasets.

Only two countries, Benin and Chile, were able to identify the existence of common identifiers between any target datasets within the Political Integrity cluster evaluated in the Barometer. The figure below illustrates these cases. Both countries maintain common identifiers for public officials and for various datasets under Political Integrity and Procurement.

Key Elements of Data Interoperability in Political Integrity Datasets

The lack of interoperability of political integrity and thematic GDB datasets points to a systematic weakness that requires action. Corruption often doesn't involve only a single act, type of act, or actor, but rather entails networks and complex money flows. Data can be critical in tracking illicit financial flows and in fighting corruption, but when the relevant data is not interoperable, only a highly fragmented picture is possible.

Land Management

The Land Management cluster explores how data can aid with one of the most contested and consequential areas of governance and regulation by illuminating who holds land and how that land is used. Transparent, accessible information on land tenure and land use is essential for promoting equitable development, resolving disputes, safeguarding the rights of communities, and ensuring sustainable resource management.

This cluster focuses on two critical dimensions: land tenure data provides insight into ownership, leases, usage rights, and customary claims, helping to clarify who has legal or recognized rights over land; land use data reveals how land is being developed or utilized, whether for agriculture, housing, commerce, conservation, or other purposes.

Together, these datasets are vital for holding governments and private actors accountable, informing fair land distribution policies, and supporting environmental and social planning. When land-related data is open and reliable, it empowers citizens, protects vulnerable communities, and supports decision-making that balances economic development with human and ecological well-being.

Land Tenure

Barometer results indicate that 30% of countries (13 of 43) have some related data available directly from the government, that 51% (22) have data available but not from the government, and 19% of countries (8) do not make any data available. Among all countries, 49% (21) have land tenure data with national coverage that is not limited to a specific area or location of the country. These specific countries were subject to further analysis by the Barometer which

indicates that even countries with national data have limited information on the land tenure of indigenous people or land tenure assigned to communal lands. 52% of countries do not have any data on indigenous land tenure, and 48% of countries do not have any data on communal lands. However, other kinds of data are more available. For example, 86% of countries have data related to natural resources.

Available Data on Land Tenure: Key Categories

In terms of open data principles, the most positive finding was that 71% of countries with national data make it available free of charge. Other findings are less positive. For example, only 5% of these countries have full historic data available, 19% of them have it fully updated, in machine-readable formats, and available as a whole.

Land Use

Barometer findings indicate that 42% of countries (18 of 43) make land use data available from the government, and that another 42% of the countries have data online but not from the government. The remaining 16% (7) do not have any data online. Among all countries with data available, 63% (27) provide data with national coverage.

Results from countries with national data coverage show some limitations on data related to the enforcement of land use zoning (33% of countries have some data) and on data related to public land use (52% of countries have some data). Other results are more. For example, 96% of countries have some kind of standardized land use dictionary, 93% of countries have source information in their metadata, and 81% of countries have some data related to non-public land use.

Available Data on Land Use: Key Categories

In terms of open data principles, only a limited few countries show full compliance. The most positive finding was that 78% of countries with national

data have made it available free of charge. However, 0% of countries have full historic data available, 11% fully comply with the machine readable principle, 15% use an open license, and 19% comply with the data available as a whole (bulk download).

On a more positive note, among countries with national coverage, land use data is utilized across a wide spectrum of actors, including government bodies, civil society, academia, media, and the private sector, serving purposes that span from policy formulation to climate action and inclusion.

In Burkina Faso, for example, the academia used this data to analyze the [tourism capacity and development](#) in specific areas of the country. In Honduras, the academia examined [urban expansion and population growth](#) in specific areas of the country to identify how they affect land use and natural resources. And in Liberia, international advocacy organizations used this data to detect high rates of [deforestation](#) of national forest areas, as well as in other countries like Côte d'Ivoire and Ghana.

Open land data is essential not only for operational efficiency and policy coherence but also for enabling a holistic understanding of the land information ecosystem. Open, interoperable, and standardized land data improves transparency, enhances cross-sectoral data integration, and supports evidence-based decision-making. It strengthens the feedback loops between stakeholders, including governments, civil society, and the private sector, thereby enabling more inclusive and sustainable development outcomes.

Barometer results indicate that there is a great deal of variation, nationally and regionally, but generally the land use data ecosystem is still very incomplete. There are multiple dimensions to land data and much more needs to be done to improve, not only, data collection, but the governance and open publication of existing digital data collections.

Charl-Thom Bayer-Land Portal

Company Information

The Company Information cluster examines the availability and openness of key datasets that help uncover who ultimately controls and benefits from corporate entities. By focusing on beneficial ownership and company registers, this cluster explores the foundations of corporate transparency, an essential component in the fight against corruption, tax evasion, and the abuse of power.

Transparent company information allows journalists, civil society, and oversight bodies to trace links between corporate structures and political influence, identify potential conflicts of interest, and expose illicit financial flows. Beneficial ownership data, in particular, plays a vital role in revealing the real people behind opaque corporate fronts, and it is especially important when those entities intersect with public procurement, political finance, or public office.

For data to serve the public good, it must be more than legally mandated, it must be accessible, timely, and usable. This cluster evaluates not only whether beneficial ownership and company data are collected by law, but also whether these datasets are open in practice and structured in ways that enable meaningful use by watchdogs, citizens, and regulators.

Company Registers

A national company register contains the details of companies that are incorporated within a country. Results from the Barometer indicate that 65% of the countries (28 of the 43) make some of this data available directly from the government, that an additional 2 have data available but not from the government. 30% of the countries (13) do not make this data accessible to the public primarily because there is no centralized national company registry, or there are login requirements that are not available to everyone, or the data is only available for government agencies.

Among the 28 countries, unique company identifiers are the most frequently available data. 93% of countries make identifier data available along with basic company information, such as the company name, legal form status, and registered address.

However, the availability of other relevant data is limited, such as the details of shareholders (25%) and company accounts (21%).

Types of Data Available in Company Registers

As for adherence to the open data principles, results reveal more weaknesses than strengths. 86% of countries that publish data do not have it available as a whole, 79% of countries do not publish in machine readable formats, and 64% of countries do not provide it under an open license. On the positive side, 75% of the countries make the data available free of charge, and 71% of them ensure it is timely and updated.

Good examples of company register data can be found in Botswana and Mexico. In Botswana, [essential details](#) like company name, legal form, status, and address are available, each company has a unique identifier and information on shareholders, including names, number of shares, and categories. There are accessible tools to explore the data, and the data is regularly updated. In Mexico, [the data](#) is provided by INEGI (the National Institute of Statistics and Geography) and is accessible online, offering geographic mapping tools to identify the location of companies. The data includes unique identifiers and basic company information.

Beneficial Ownership

In general, Barometer findings indicate that LAC and African countries are generally advancing in terms of their beneficial ownership legal frameworks, but there is still plenty of room for improvement. The average score for Latin America was 49.17 and, for Africa, 47.33. Only 37% (that is 16 out of 43) of countries explicitly require the publication of beneficial ownership data, while 88% (that is 38 out of 43) of them make it mandatory to collect this information. In practice, beneficial ownership information is collected by the majority of countries but only disclosed by a minority. Furthermore, results related to data publication indicate that only 7% of countries actually make any data public.

Among the 88% of countries with frameworks, results indicate that clear definitions on what constitutes ownership are provided in 87% of them, and that clear definitions on control are provided in 76%. On the other hand, only 21% of countries have rules or processes to protect beneficial owners from having some or all of their data published.

Beneficial Ownership Regulatory Frameworks: Definitions and Protection

In terms of provisions for data quality, results indicate that 82% of countries require beneficial ownership data to be regularly updated, and 79% require this data to be collected in a centralized register. In addition, 61% have specified an agency responsible for ensuring data collection and quality.

Public accessibility is an overall weakness as it is only explicitly required in 11% of countries.

Beneficial Ownership Regulatory Frameworks: Provisions for Data Quality

Beneficial ownership data is only available to the public in [Ecuador](#), [Nigeria](#), and Ghana. In Ghana, the data is only required for [extractive industries](#). In Ecuador and Nigeria, unique identifiers are assigned to companies, and the data is maintained up to date and available free of charge. In Nigeria, the data is provided through the Persons of Significant Control (PSC) register, adheres to the Beneficial Ownership Data Standard (BODS), and is available in machine-readable formats like JSON and CSV. In terms of beneficial ownership framework, an illustrative example can be found in the Bahamas, the [Register of Beneficial Ownership Act](#) and its [Amendment](#) require the registration of beneficial owners and sets up a national database.

Transparency in the business environment is not a given. Researchers can support the continued health of the company information ecosystem through work that demonstrates, documents, and measures the impact of governments, businesses, and citizens having access to accurate, complete, and high-quality information on companies and the people who own, control, or benefit from them. This type of research is an essential contribution to keeping the policy space open and for reforms to be sustained.

The Barometer is an invaluable resource in these efforts. Already, it is being used in academic research to [explore patterns](#) and motives for beneficial ownership reform. Over the coming years, Open Ownership and partners will be working to expand the evidence base to impact transparency in BO networks, and how different sources of information—including information about BO of legal vehicles and shareholders—can most effectively contribute to having a better understanding of these networks.

Alanna Markle-Open Ownership

Public Procurement

The Public Procurement cluster assesses whether national procurement systems support transparency and the availability of structured, open, and publicly accessible data. A new indicator in this edition examines whether legal and regulatory frameworks require the publication of procurement information and whether the data covers the full procurement lifecycle: from planning and tender to contract award and implementation. The cluster also considers critical aspects of data governance, including the presence of unique identifiers, the potential for interlinking datasets, and adherence to open data standards that enhance usability and analysis.

To truly serve the public good, procurement data must be released in formats that enable journalists, civil society, and oversight bodies to follow the money, identify red flags, and hold actors accountable. Transparent procurement systems are vital for ensuring fair competition, improving public service delivery, and building trust between governments and citizens.

Governance

In general, 2nd Edition findings indicate that Latin American and African countries have achieved strong progress in the implementation of regulatory frameworks around procurement data. The average score for LAC was 78.16, and for Africa, 75.79. 100% of the countries examined (excluding Liberia as its framework is not applied nationally) explicitly require the publication of procurement data within their frameworks, and results illustrate full compliance with 100% of the countries effectively publishing procurement data for the general public.

However, a deeper analysis of the legal frameworks implemented to date indicates areas for improvement. For example, 67% of countries do not require the use of data standards, 36% do not require the implementation-stage procurement data to be published, and 26% do not require data on direct awards to be published.

Public Procurement Regulatory Frameworks: Definitions, Process Types, and Required Data Fields

Results indicate that provisions for data quality within the frameworks in place are fairly strong with 90% of the countries having a lead agency specifically responsible for the accurate and timely publication of procurement data, 83% of them explicitly requiring the digital collection of procurement data, and 76% of them having a verification process defined by law before data is published.

Public Procurement Regulatory Frameworks: Provisions for Ensuring Data Quality

Good examples of public procurement frameworks can be found in the Dominican Republic and Rwanda. In the Dominican Republic, [Law 340-06](#) requires that all information be publicly accessible, [Decree 416-23](#) stipulates preventive monitoring by the Procurement Directorate to ensure compliance with laws and regulations, while [Decree 350-17](#) mandates the compulsory use of the Transactional Portal for procurement activities, which uses the Open Contracting Data Standard. In Rwanda, [Law N° 031/2022](#) and Ministerial [Order N° 001/23/10/TC](#) require data collection and publication for goods, services, and public works, covering the stages of planning, tender, award and implementation, while supporting digital data collection and regular updates.

Availability

In terms of data availability, Barometer results indicate a positive performance by 42 countries with regard to the range of procurement data made available. 93% of countries publish data on the procurement of goods and services. It is important to note that only 14% of countries release data on the implementation stage, reflecting a significant area for improvement.

Procurement Data Availability: Key Data Types

As for adherence to open data principles, results of the 2nd Edition present both positive and negative findings on the assessed countries. On the positive side, 100% of countries offer procurement data free of charge, 74% update the data, and 67% offer historical data. However, 55% of countries do not offer the data as-a-whole, 40% do not offer the data in machine readable formats, and 33% do not offer it under an open license.

Good examples of public procurement data can be found in Ecuador and Kenya. In Ecuador, public procurement data has two main sources, the [Official Public Procurement System of Ecuador \(SOCE\)](#) and the Open Data Portal for Public Procurement, which cover all procurement stages and provide unique identifiers for companies and historical and structured data that aligns with the Open Contracting Data Standard. In Kenya, the [public procurement portal](#) publishes data in machine-readable formats, containing identifiers to connect data on each stage of a single procurement process, and adhering to the Open Contracting Data Standard.

While there are good examples in both regions on how to disclose procurement data in an open format following international best practices, there are still huge gaps in terms of the disclosure of data from all stages of the contracting process in a machine-readable format.

Countries need to continue to increase the availability of information both in terms of key fields of information, as well as the overall coverage of the data included. Without that information, users will struggle to track how governments are spending and delivering goods and public services to citizens.

No country should rely on its current assessment. As data availability and quality continue to improve, the opportunities increase for all actors to use public procurement data to deliver better public services, goods, and infrastructure for inclusive, fair, and sustainable communities.

Camila Salazar - Open Contracting Partnership

Public Finance

The Public Finance cluster assesses the availability and governance of budget and spending data—key to understanding how public resources are managed and whether fiscal decisions serve the public good. Transparent financial data allows citizens, oversight bodies, and civil society to follow the money: to see how budgets are formulated, how funds are allocated, and how spending aligns with stated priorities.

This cluster examines not only whether budget and spending data are published, but also how they are governed, whether legal frameworks guarantee transparency, whether the data is timely and complete, and whether mechanisms exist to ensure public access and usability. These dimensions are essential for transforming fiscal data into a tool for accountability, participation, and more effective policy implementation.

Governance

Most countries have a legal framework to guide public financial management. These frameworks determine how government income, debt, budget, spending, and other public finance information, such as budgetary performance indicators or measurements, should be collected, managed, and reported. The Barometer evaluates whether the existing frameworks in place within a given country adequately address the collection and publication of key structured data to support the management of public finances and whether this data is available to the general public.

In general, findings show that LAC and African countries have achieved some progress in the development and implementation of legal and regulatory frameworks related to public finance. The average score for LAC was 62.00 and, for Africa, 68.59. A total of 95% of countries explicitly require that finance data has to be published, and 93% have published at least some data, illustrating fairly strong compliance.

However, a deeper analysis into the existing frameworks in place also indicates some weaknesses. Less than 50% of countries explicitly require structured data to be published with the approved budget as the most

required dataset (47% of countries). Other datasets are far less often required with only 37% of countries requiring budget proposals and financial summary reports to be published.

Types of Public Finance Data Required by Regulatory Frameworks

On a more positive note, Barometer findings do indicate the existence of provisions for data quality. For example, 84% of countries have a dedicated agency responsible for the accurate and timely publication of data, and 80% of countries explicitly require this data to be regularly updated.

Some examples of robust frameworks are available in Honduras, Ghana and South Africa. In Ghana, the Public Financial Management Act (along with the [Public Financial Management Regulations](#)) provides direction on the data responsibilities during budget preparation, enactment, execution, and reporting. And in South Africa, the [Public Finance Management Act](#) requires data collection and reporting by government departments and entities; the [Municipal Finance Management Act](#) applies these requirements to municipalities; and the [National Treasury Regulations](#) provides detailed guidelines for financial data collection and reporting, collectively promoting transparency and accountability in public financial management.

Availability

In terms of data availability, only 3 countries do not have any public finance data available for the general public: Liberia, Rwanda and Tunisia. However, among the other 40 countries where data has been made available as a result of government action, the range and quality of data is extremely limited. For example, extrabudgetary spending data is only available in a structured manner from 23% of countries, and amended budget data is only available in 28% of countries. However, as noted, approved budget data is available in 93% of countries examined (40% structured and 53% non-structured) and similarly, budget proposal data is available in 88% of countries (43% structured and 45% non-structured).

Types of Public Finance Data Available

In terms of the alignment with open data principles, Barometer results for public finance data reveal significant incongruities. While 100% of the

countries that publish this data are doing it free of charge, and 90% of them have historical data available, the data is not actually machine readable in 48% of the countries, in 70%, the data is not available as-a-whole, and in 60%, the data is not openly licensed.

The weaknesses around the limitations of legal frameworks to ensure data availability substantially limits the use of public finance data for greater transparency, improved public financial management, and budget allocation. Structured and disaggregated data can be used to support gender budget analysis, green budget analysis, and an evaluation of the impact of fiscal policy on minorities and marginalized groups.

Nevertheless, good examples of public finance data availability can be seen in Guatemala and Argentina. In Guatemala, the Ministry of Finance provides budget and spending data free of charge via the [Open Data platform](#); structured data is regularly updated, historically comprehensive, and available in machine-readable formats with bulk download options and tools for exploration. In Argentina, the [Open Budget Portal](#) allows access to structured budgets and spending data along with different ways to explore the data.

Fiscal data is foundational to a transparent, equitable, and resilient public sector. Informed budget decisions, public trust, and effective policy design all depend on timely, comprehensive, and accessible public finance information. In recent years, this need has only intensified as governments face heightened fiscal pressures from inflation, debt, climate risks, and public service demands.

The Barometer Public Finance cluster indicates that fiscal transparency is moving in the right direction – though significant implementation deficits persist. Stronger legal frameworks are emerging, but data availability reveals substantial lags.

Some reforms are driven more by individual leadership rather than by institutional guarantees. The task ahead is to embed transparency into systems and laws that endure. By expanding access to structured, timely, and comprehensive fiscal data, governments can empower citizens, build trust, and deliver better policy outcomes. However, such transformations require investment, coordination, and political commitment.

Aura Martínez and Raúl Castellanos-Consultants
Global Initiative for Fiscal Transparency

Observations

These thematic clusters shed light on the state of data across critical policy areas, while also revealing systemic enablers and constraints that cut across sectors. One of the clearest patterns emerging from the Barometer is the foundational role of governance in shaping data availability and vice versa. Across regions and themes, strong governance frameworks consistently correspond with higher levels of available and usable public data. Building on this insight, the Barometer has examined the relationship between the quality of data governance and the availability of public data more closely. As observed in the 1st Edition, a positive correlation remains between governance and availability. This relationship is strong ($r=0.837$), reaffirming that governance frameworks play a significant role in ensuring access. However, it is also shaped by differences in countries' underlying capabilities.

The scatter plot below illustrates the overall trend: higher governance scores tend to be associated with higher levels of availability. Yet, within this broad pattern, differences emerge. For example, many countries in the Lower Capability group exhibit similar availability scores, typically clustered between 20 and 30, but their governance scores vary widely, from around 30 to 50. Most of these countries are located in Africa, where there is a notable pattern: secondary enablers, such as internet access and the establishment of digital government institutions have improved, while key capability-related indicators have weakened. This highlights a crucial insight that investments in digital infrastructure alone do not lead to greater availability unless they are supported by institutional, human, and financial efforts to enable meaningful implementation.

Exploring the Relationship Between Governance and Data Availability Scores

To examine this relationship in greater detail, the Barometer analyzed all matched governance and availability indicator pairs across the Barometer⁹.

⁹ In this analysis, the correlation between governance and data availability is based on a structured classification of both legal frameworks and data access. To assess availability, datasets are classified as: *Open Data*, which refers to data available online, has representative coverage, and meets strict openness criteria; *Some Data*, where the data is accessible and representative but not fully open; and *No Data*, indicating either complete unavailability or limited coverage. On the governance side, we evaluate the existence and nature of publication requirements through a tiered lens. *No Requirement* signifies that no governance framework mandates publication. *Data Requirement* refers to frameworks that exist but do not explicitly require open data publication. In contrast, *Open Data Requirement* indicates a governance framework that explicitly mandates the open publication of data. By aligning these classifications, analysis reveals whether stronger governance mechanisms, particularly those explicitly requiring open data, are associated with higher levels of data availability.

Linking Regulation to Practice: Correlation Between Data Requirements and Availability

An analysis of all governance and availability indicator pairs illustrates that stronger data requirements are generally associated with greater data availability. In 95.28% of countries where no governance framework mandates data collection or publication, no data is made available. When the publication of data is required by governance frameworks, 62.09% of countries make data available in some form and 9.15% ensure the data meets the open definition¹⁰. This still leaves an implementation gap in 28.76% of cases where governance frameworks require publication of data. The implementation gap is larger when it comes to open data in that only 39.13% of binding requirements to publish open data appear to result in open data being available, although some data is available in 56.52% of these countries.

¹⁰ It is important to note that identifying “open data requirements” in this edition is more complex. The original existence indicator that explicitly captured open data requirements is no longer part of the framework. Instead, we rely on the ‘public_access’ question, which includes a supporting field asking whether the data is open. However, this is a **text-based field**, and responses often lack a clear yes/no designation. For the current analysis, we have categorized all “Yes” and “Partially” responses to the public_access question as indicating the **presence of an open data requirement**.

Cross-cutting Analysis

Cross-cutting Analysis

Not all foundational elements of sound data governance can be effectively addressed by focusing on specific indicators or action areas. Integrating cross-cutting themes like Data Foundations for AI, Inclusion, and Use of Data, into the Barometer's analysis provides a lens for assessing the broader societal implications of data governance and availability. By examining these themes, the Barometer is able to provide a richer and more insightful analysis of how data is being used for the public good and highlight how robust data foundations are essential for fostering healthy and sustainable data ecosystems.

Data Foundations for AI

The 2nd Edition of the Global Data Barometer integrates artificial intelligence (AI) as a cross-cutting theme, exploring how emerging technologies are shaping, and being shaped by, national data ecosystems. Through a set of targeted sub-questions, the Barometer examines how AI intersects with key components of data governance, such as data protection, data sharing, data literacy, and data reuse. Complementary secondary indicators provide additional depth, allowing for a broader understanding of how countries are preparing for and implementing AI-related policies and practices. This approach helps highlight both areas of advancement and where further attention is needed to ensure that data foundations can effectively support the responsible use of AI.

One area of growing focus is the provision of AI-related training and capacity building. Evidence suggests that many governments and institutions are beginning to incorporate AI into public-sector learning, often through collaborations with universities and expert organizations. In some instances, freely accessible online platforms like Coursera are being used to broaden access to training. While these are promising developments, opportunities can still be unevenly distributed. In some cases, courses have been tailored primarily for senior officials. Expanding access across all levels of public administration will be important to fully embed AI literacy and ensure widespread readiness.

AI in Public Sector Training: Percentage of Programs Covering AI Topics

In parallel, many governments are advancing strategies to encourage data reuse. Among the 21 countries where such support is evident, a few have begun to include explicit references to AI or algorithmic systems. While still limited, these examples represent early steps toward aligning data and AI governance. Continued refinement and clearer guidance could help more countries develop comprehensive strategies that integrate AI into broader data policy frameworks.

Legal frameworks are also evolving to reflect the growing importance of AI. More than half of the countries reviewed have introduced references to algorithmic decision-making into their data protection legislation. Notably, African countries show relatively strong engagement on this front with a higher proportion including such provisions when compared to countries in LAC. This trend may reflect regional leadership, increased awareness of AI's policy relevance, or the influence of international legal standards. As more countries consider how to regulate algorithmic processes, these examples may offer valuable lessons and momentum.

Percentage of Data Protection Laws Addressing Algorithmic Decision-Making

At the same time, data sharing frameworks present an opportunity for further development. Most existing frameworks do not yet explicitly address AI-related issues, pointing to the potential for policy innovation. Incorporating AI considerations into data sharing can strengthen oversight and help governments anticipate ethical and operational challenges. As AI continues to evolve, updating frameworks to include clear guidance on its use will become increasingly important for maintaining trust and accountability.

Finally, while there is currently limited documentation on AI tools being used as interfaces within government data systems, this likely reflects an early stage of adoption rather than a lack of activity. As governments explore new applications of machine learning and AI to enhance public-sector performance, further research will be needed to capture and assess these efforts. The coming years may see significant growth in this area, offering valuable opportunities to harness AI for more effective, transparent, and inclusive data governance.

Implications for Data for AI

The Barometer's analysis reveals that while many countries are beginning to integrate AI into their data ecosystems, this progress is still uneven and fragmented. AI training efforts, though emerging, often remain limited in reach and accessibility, leaving large portions of the public sector without adequate preparation. At the policy level, most national data strategies and sharing frameworks lack explicit guidance on algorithmic governance, creating a gap between data use ambitions and responsible AI oversight. Data protection laws show more progress, particularly in Africa, where references to algorithmic decision-making are more common, but significant regional disparities remain. These patterns underscore the need for more inclusive capacity-building initiatives, stronger alignment between AI and broader data governance frameworks, and enhanced legal protections to address the risks associated with automated systems.

Improving the visibility of AI adoption within public institutions and fostering collaboration across regions will be essential to build trustworthy, context-sensitive AI governance. The current moment offers a critical opportunity to shape frameworks that are grounded in public values and designed to advance transparency, equity, and the public good.

Inclusion

Inclusion is a vital cross-cutting theme that centres on accessibility and equitable participation, examining how well data ecosystems enable all segments of the population to access, use, and benefit from data, thereby promoting equity and addressing systemic disparities. In the 2nd Edition, newly refined questions and sub-questions provide deeper insights into how countries work to support accessibility, not only for people with disabilities but also for communities with different linguistic profiles, highlighting both the challenges and opportunities for more inclusive data environments.

Accessibility

Overall, the Barometer findings indicate a lack of comprehensive legal or regulatory frameworks that specifically address the inclusion of persons with disabilities with regard to data. While some countries have adopted measures to promote digital accessibility more broadly, very few have detailed provisions that directly link disability inclusion with data governance, collection, or use.

In comparative terms, LAC tends to perform somewhat better than Africa in this area with more countries in the region adopting specific frameworks. However, even in these cases, the frameworks often focus on general digital accessibility and compliance with Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (e.g. [WCAG 2.0 or 2.1](#)) without detailing specific requirements for accessible data collection, consent mechanisms, or correction procedures. These standards are commonly implemented as technical guidance rather than through binding legal mandates.

Breakdown of Elements in the Accessibility Indicator

In addition to WCAG, the two most widely used types of frameworks supporting inclusion and equitable access in the data contexts are:

- **National Disability Legislation** – These frameworks establish core rights for persons with disabilities and typically mandate accessibility standards for public services and communications. They often require the use of alternative formats or other accommodations (e.g., braille, sign language interpretation) to ensure equitable access.
- **Access to Information Laws** – While primarily governing governmental transparency and public information dissemination, these laws may implicitly require accessible data publication; however, few explicitly address disability-inclusive data practices or mandate accessible formats in data disclosure.

Examples of good practices include Brazil’s legal framework which requires the inclusion of people with disabilities in terms of digital access to information and communication ([Statute of Persons with Disabilities](#) and [eMAG](#)), Peru’s laws ([29973](#) and [law 28530](#)) that require internet portals to have accessibility systems to include people with disabilities. Additionally, the [Kenya National Disability Policy 2024](#) outlines the government’s commitment to promoting the rights and inclusion of persons with disabilities. Across both regions examined by the Barometer, there is limited evidence of institutional mechanisms to review and enforce accessibility in data governance, such as cross-government coordination to ensure compliance with standards like

WCAG 2.2 or mandates for universal design in data infrastructure. While some positive examples exist, particularly where disability rights laws intersect with broader digital inclusion policies, there remains a significant gap in ensuring that data governance frameworks meaningfully include and accommodate persons with disabilities.

Language

The findings from the Barometer highlight a recurring theme across multiple countries that while data is often available in one official language, the data is not available in other widely spoken national, regional, or indigenous languages, creating significant accessibility barriers. This underscores the need for multilingual approaches in data publication to ensure that all segments of the population can effectively engage with public data.

A key issue identified is the dominance of official languages that are frequently colonial languages, such as English, French, or Spanish. While many countries have multiple official or national languages, data publication often remains confined to just one dominant language. This limits access for communities that primarily speak other national or regional languages.

Another significant concern is the exclusion of indigenous languages. Even in cases where these languages have official recognition, they are often not included in data collection or publication efforts. This exclusion represents a failure to fully embrace linguistic diversity and can marginalize significant portions of the population who rely on these languages for information and civic participation.

The distinction between de facto and official languages further complicates data accessibility. In countries like Ghana, for example, Twi is widely spoken, yet official data is primarily available in English. Similarly, in Senegal, Wolof is the most commonly spoken language, but French remains the primary language for official documents and data. This discrepancy highlights a misalignment between the language used in daily life and the language used in government data dissemination.

Accessibility barriers were a common concern among researchers as publishing data in a single language limits engagement for non-speakers. When data is only available in one language, especially if that language is not

widely spoken by the majority, it reduces public participation and the ability of communities to use data for decision-making and advocacy.

Despite these challenges, some countries have taken proactive steps to improve language inclusivity in data publication. Tunisia, for instance, provides data in both Arabic and French. Rwanda has made a notable effort by publishing data in [Kinyarwanda, English, and French](#), ensuring broader accessibility, although it does not publish in Swahili. These inconsistencies persist in many countries. In Kenya, for example, Swahili is a national language alongside English, yet government data is available only in English. Similarly, Morocco does not cover Tamazight in its data publications, despite its status as an [official language](#). Additionally, many countries continue to use English as the primary language for government data, even though it is not the most widely spoken language among the population.

These findings emphasize the need for governments to adopt more inclusive language policies in data publication. Ensuring that data is available in multiple languages, particularly those spoken by large segments of the population, is crucial for fostering transparency, inclusivity, and effective public engagement.

Implications for Inclusion and Equitable Access

The findings from this edition of the Barometer reveal a persistent and multifaceted gap in how governments ensure inclusive and equitable access to data. While many countries have made commitments to digital inclusion, often through general disability legislation or transparency laws, these rarely translate into specific, enforceable measures that guarantee accessibility or linguistic inclusion in data governance practices.

In terms of accessibility, legal and policy frameworks tend to focus on broad digital access or compliance with standards like the WCAG. However, few address the full data lifecycle, from collection and consent to publication and correction, with persons with disabilities in mind. While countries like Peru and Brazil offer promising examples of inclusive practices, such cases remain the exception. Overall, implementation is uneven and institutional mechanisms for oversight and enforcement are limited. In many contexts, accessibility is framed more as a technical recommendation than a binding legal obligation.

Language inclusion presents a parallel challenge. While data is often published in an official language, the exclusion of widely spoken national, regional, or indigenous languages significantly restricts access for large segments of the population. This dynamic is especially stark in multilingual contexts, where dominant or colonial languages like English, French, or Spanish overshadow the linguistic realities of everyday civic life. Some countries, like Rwanda, Namibia, and Botswana, have taken steps toward multilingual data publication, but these remain exceptions rather than the norm.

The convergence of these two dimensions, accessibility for persons with disabilities and linguistic inclusion, illustrates a broader issue: data systems are too often designed without consideration of the diversity of end users. This undermines the transformative potential of public data to empower communities, inform decision-making, and foster participation.

To close these gaps, countries must move beyond symbolic commitments and integrate inclusion into the foundations of their data systems by enacting binding regulations that require accessible and multilingual formats, by investing in the institutional capacity to implement and monitor these standards, and by treating inclusion not as a secondary consideration but as a core element of effective and equitable data governance.

Inclusive data systems are not only more just, they are also more useful, more widely adopted, and ultimately more impactful. Ensuring equitable access is a critical step toward realizing the full public value of data.

Use of Data

Measuring the impact of public data use remains a complex challenge, often reliant on case studies that lack scalability and comparability. Inconsistent documentation across countries frequently skews the evidence, overrepresenting regions with stronger reporting practices. Drawing on lessons from the 1st Edition, the 2nd Edition of the Barometer treats data use as a cross-cutting theme, enabling a more holistic understanding of how data functions within and across different sectors.

By embedding data use across thematic action areas, a more nuanced, qualitative picture is possible of how data is being applied in diverse contexts. Encouragingly, this edition's results point to notable progress in data availability, especially for Budget & Spending and Public Procurement, two areas that continue to stand out across regions. This progress reflects sustained efforts to improve transparency and bolster public sector accountability; however, availability alone is insufficient.

Where data is accessible, it is increasingly being used, particularly by civil society organizations and the media. These actors play a pivotal role in holding institutions accountable by using data for investigative journalism, public awareness, and oversight initiatives, such as red flag analyses to uncover corruption, mismanagement, or conflicts of interest.

For instance, the civil society organization, Participación Ciudadana, in the Dominican Republic used budget and spending data to produce the report ["Mapping the Flow of Finances for Climate Change Projects in the Dominican Republic"](#), focusing specifically on accountability and transparency in climate financing. Similarly, in Jamaica, the Jamaica Accountability Meter Portal (JAMP) created a [Budget Tracker](#) that translates complex financial information into accessible formats to support public engagement and oversight.

From Availability to Use: Percentage of Documented Data Use Cases

The Barometer reveals diverse usage patterns across different stakeholder groups to support accountability efforts. Civil society and media often adopt broad oversight roles, whereas other actors demonstrate more specialized applications. The private sector, for example, leverages Company Register and Public Procurement data for due diligence, risk analysis, and identifying business opportunities. In these cases, data serves not just as a transparency mechanism, but also as a valuable tool for strategic decision-making.

Governments function both as providers and users of data. Internal use of datasets, such as Company Register, Budget & Spending, and Procurement data, often support regulatory compliance, planning, and performance monitoring, reinforcing the role of open data in strengthening institutional capacity. In Chile, for example, the Comptroller General of the Republic uses the asset declarations portal to [monitor government ministers' assets](#) for irregularities and to identify officials who have failed to declare. This illustrates how both oversight bodies and the media draw on the same datasets for different but complementary purposes.

Academia, meanwhile, applies datasets to inform policy research, assess institutional performance, and generate evidence for reform, thus contributing to a broader knowledge base for public sector innovation.

Each type of data reflects a different governance challenge or opportunity; Budget and Spending data supports fiscal monitoring and citizen engagement; Political Finance data fosters electoral integrity; Procurement data highlights inefficiencies or favoritism; Interest and Asset Declarations aim to expose conflicts of interest; and Right to Information performance data gauges institutional transparency and responsiveness.

These varied use cases emphasize the need for open data ecosystems that are not only accessible but also attuned to the practical needs of diverse users. They illustrate how data use can evolve to serve the public good from uncovering power asymmetries to supporting inclusive, evidence-based policy. For example, in Angola and Mozambique, budget data is used to promote accountability and advocate for better resource allocation in education, health, and social protection. In Angola, activities include [efforts](#) to ensure that public funds effectively reach children, while in Mozambique, data is used to [highlight discrepancies](#) in the General State Account and support calls for better transparency. Meanwhile in Senegal, organizations like BudgIT Senegal simplify budget data for citizen engagement with initiatives, such as the [Youth Budget Club](#), to build budget literacy and promote civic accountability.

Yet, no thematic area to date shows full utilization, revealing an ongoing significant untapped potential. Strengthening underdeveloped areas, such as Beneficial Ownership and Lobbying data, remains crucial for comprehensive oversight. To fully realize this potential, we must address persistent barriers

by improving data literacy, strengthening institutional capacity, and ensuring that access translates into meaningful use.

Implications for Use of Data

The Barometer highlights several countries where strong data availability is matched by active use to support greater government accountability. In LAC, countries like Chile, Ecuador, Brazil, Mexico, the Dominican Republic, Argentina, and Peru demonstrate robust engagement across multiple thematic areas. In Africa, countries, such as South Africa, Rwanda, and Senegal, show promising signs of aligning data availability with use, illustrating the value of connecting data efforts with user communities.

Moving forward, promoting cross-regional learning, supporting a wider range of user groups, and reinforcing accountability-oriented data use are essential strategies for maximizing the value of open data. By building on existing momentum, and nurturing ecosystems where data is both available and actively used, countries can move closer to a future where data supports inclusive development, democratic governance, and the public good.

Regional Analysis

Regional Analysis

The 2nd edition of the Global Data Barometer focuses on Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC) and Africa – two regions where data governance ecosystems are undergoing complex and often uneven transformations. By analyzing regional performance, the Barometer provides more contextualized and actionable findings, grounded in nationally representative data practices that reflect scalable, system-wide efforts rather than isolated initiatives.

Across LAC and Africa, we observe a dynamic interplay of progress and persistent challenges in data governance. In both regions, financial transparency and anti-corruption efforts have gained traction with several countries prioritizing openness in public procurement and public finance. These developments reflect a growing recognition of the role data can play in strengthening institutional accountability.

In Latin America, significant strides have been made in civic transparency and institutional capacity, particularly through advances in right to information, oversight of political financing, and civil service training. However, these gains are tempered by setbacks in areas such as company registration and beneficial ownership data, exposing the fragility of reforms that depend on sustained political and financial commitment. The Caribbean, while facing distinct governance realities, shares many of Latin America's systemic challenges. The region as a whole has made notable progress in building digital infrastructure and advancing data protection and literacy, yet it continues to lag in politically sensitive domains such as lobbying transparency and land data – highlighting enduring gaps in democratic accountability.

In Africa, improvements in financial governance and the implementation of anti-corruption tools stand out, particularly in the context of public procurement and budget transparency. However, these advances coexist with setbacks in open data initiatives and limited training programs, illustrating the challenges of maintaining holistic support for data systems. The uneven pace of digital transformation, shaped by resource constraints, infrastructural deficits, and evolving regulatory frameworks, further complicates the regional landscape.

Taken together, these regional trajectories highlight both the drivers of progress and the barriers that remain in building inclusive, sustainable data ecosystems. By focusing on the shared and context-specific dynamics within LAC and Africa, the Barometer provides regionally grounded insights into where strategic interventions can foster greater equity, resilience, and democratic data use.

Latin America and the Caribbean

Country	Comparative strength	Comparative weakness	National score
Argentina	Capability (C): Open data initiative		
Bahamas	Governance (CI): Beneficial ownership		
Barbados	Governance (G): Data protection		
Belize	Governance (G): Data sharing frameworks		
Bolivia	Availability (PI): Asset declarations	Governance (G): Data protection	24.81
Brazil	Governance (G): Accessibility coverage & data		
Chile	Availability (PI): Lobbying data		
Colombia	Capability (C): Government support for re-use	Governance (G): Accessibility coverage & data	61.22
Costa Rica	Governance (G): Data sharing frameworks	Capability (C): Open data initiative	37.49
Dominican Republic	Capability (C): Civil service Training		
Ecuador	Availability (CI): Company register	Governance (PI): Lobbying register	58.98
El Salvador	Availability (PI): RTI performance data	Availability (PP): Public procurement data	22.23
Guatemala	Governance (PI): Political finance		
Honduras	Governance (PF): Public finance data		
Jamaica	Governance (G): Open data policy		
Mexico	Availability (CI): Company register	Governance (CI): Beneficial ownership	62.51
Panama	Capability (C): Open data initiative		
Paraguay	Capability (C): Open data initiative		
Peru	Availability (PI): Political finance data	Governance (PI): Asset declarations	55.31
Trinidad and Tobago	Governance (PP) Public procurement data		
Uruguay	Capability (C): Government support for re-use		

Hub Perspectives

Iniciativa Latinoamericana por los Datos Abiertos ILDA (Latin America)
/Gloria Guerrero

In a world where data is becoming a key asset for public and private decision-making, countries face a common challenge: building strong, reliable, and democratically aligned open data ecosystems. In Latin America this task unfolds within a complex context marked by deep social inequalities, institutional instability, digital divides, and, at the same time, innovative experiences of openness, participation, and social justice driven at the local level.

The region is undergoing a rapid transformation in terms of digital governance. Governments, civil society organizations, academia, and multilateral institutions have worked over the past decade to promote legal frameworks around access to information, personal data protection, and open data. However, these efforts do not always translate into consistent practices or sustainable policies, resulting in a persistent gap between regulation and implementation.

Insights

One of the most notable findings comes from the overall country scores, where Brazil stands out with 66.85 the highest in the region while El Salvador registers just 23.02. This wide gap reflects

structural inequalities, where some countries have managed to develop stronger regulatory, technical, and institutional frameworks, while others still face significant barriers related to resources, capacity, and political will.

According to the methodology of this tool, the data is structured from general to specific: thematic clusters, action areas, and indicators. At first glance, it may seem most straightforward to focus on overall country scores. However, analyzing the results by thematic cluster is particularly valuable, as it allows us to identify specific sectors, opportunities, and challenges in areas such as Public Procurement, Public Finance, Governance Foundations, Critical Competencies, Political Integrity, Equitable Access, Company Information, and Land Management. These results help paint a detailed picture of the broader Latin American context and support efforts to develop impactful regional advocacy strategies.

The Barometer's methodology enables a thematic zoom that helps identify which sectors have made the most progress in terms of functionality within the data ecosystem. The highest-performing area reaches 72.7 points and relates to Public Procurement, while the lowest just 27.3 points is tied to Land Management.

Looking at the action areas, the most significant advances are seen in Public Procurement, which exceeds 70 points. However, other key areas, such as dataset interoperability within the Political Integrity cluster, a strategic function for effective data governance score as low as 1.6. This confirms a well-known challenge: the region has made progress in establishing legal and policy frameworks but continues to struggle with sustained implementation and the coordination of multiple stakeholders. This remains a key area of concern.

At the indicator level, Chile stands out in lobbying register, scoring above 90 points, highlighting major progress in areas such as open data availability and transparency policies. However, the regional average remains much lower: Mexico follows with only 29.15 points, suggesting that many of these policies are not yet widely adopted and do not translate into tangible improvements across the region.

Overall, the data presented by the Barometer suggests that many countries have adopted open data and digital government strategies, but implementation lags behind. This reveals a clear path forward to strengthen collaboration, coordination, and resource investment.

What's next?

It is important to understand and disseminate the results of tools like this one for several reasons. First, they help make visible the progress

that often goes unnoticed in global data governance debates, which tend to focus predominantly on countries in the Global North. Second, they enable the construction of a more informed regional dialogue, grounded in comparable evidence that can foster learning from good practices and support collective efforts to address shared challenges. Finally, this data provides a foundation for demanding clearer commitments from governments and multilateral organizations in the development of data policies grounded in human rights.

From a Latin American perspective, participation in initiatives of this nature should also serve as an opportunity to critically reflect on the assumptions underpinning certain global metrics. What does “good data use” mean in contexts of poverty, violence, or structural exclusion? How can we ensure that digitalization does not deepen existing inequalities? What roles are afforded to marginalized communities, Indigenous peoples, or youth in these assessments?

Understanding the state of data and its governance is especially critical in the current context of rapid development and adoption of artificial intelligence across the public and private sectors. Ensuring the availability of high-quality, representative data — under a framework of democratic data governance — can help address issues such as bias and inequality in AI systems. The findings from this second edition of the Global Data Barometer show that Latin America has made

significant progress in building an institutional foundation for open and responsible data governance. However, there is still considerable work to be done in terms of data quality, availability, use, and impact — particularly in domains that are key to inclusive development, such as gender equality, environmental action, and anti-corruption.

This conversation is both urgent and necessary in today's context, where data constitutes the foundational input for artificial intelligence and public digital infrastructure initiatives. Only through an ethical, transparent, and participatory approach to data governance can we ensure that the development of new technologies and systems is inclusive and equitable

Undoubtedly, the region has much to contribute to the global debate: experiences of territorially grounded open data initiatives, participatory processes for public policy development, and an active civil society that has championed transparency as a tool for transformation. Integrating these experiences and realities into global instruments will not only enrich measurement frameworks but also shape the future direction of global data governance.

Hub Perspectives

Caribbean Open Institute (The Caribbean)
/Suzana Russell and Lila Rao-Graham

The 2nd Edition of the Global Data Barometer includes data from five Caribbean countries: Jamaica, Bahamas, Trinidad and Tobago, Dominican Republic, and Barbados. Among these, the Dominican Republic and Jamaica stand out as regional leaders in data openness and infrastructure with scores that surpass both the Caribbean and the 2nd Edition averages. This reflects stronger political will and institutional capacity to promote data transparency.

One of the most promising areas in the region is public procurement, where consistent progress is improving accountability and reducing corruption risks in government contracting. The region also scored well in data infrastructure, indicating growing technical capacity for open data management. In terms of core competencies, internet access scored well, reflecting strong digital capability across the region, even though access disparities persist in rural and underserved areas.

Despite these bright spots, the Caribbean faces serious challenges in political accountability. Key indicators related to political integrity and land management score low across most countries, underscoring ongoing policy and implementation gaps that hinder transparency, civic engagement and inclusive governance.

Key Trends in the Caribbean

The Caribbean displays uneven progress across data governance, capabilities, and availability. Public procurement achieved the highest scores regionally, consistently ranking well across all five countries, indicating a strong regional emphasis on transparency in government contracting.

Looking more closely at the action areas, the region shows strength in digital infrastructure with a regional score of 65.35. High scores in internet access, data literacy, and data protection point to a strong foundation for digital transformation. However, the region scored low in politically sensitive areas, such as lobbying, land use, and political integrity interoperability, revealing a critical transparency gap.

Main Highlights from the Barometer

The Dominican Republic and Jamaica lead the region in overall Global Data Barometer scores, surpassing regional averages, an achievement linked to stronger institutional frameworks and national data policies. Among thematic clusters, public procurement emerged as the strongest area, with a regional average of 61.64, reflecting robust legal and implementation practices in public procurement data. The region also

demonstrated technical readiness for open data ecosystems, as evidenced by a score of 65.35 in data infrastructure. Internet access topped the capability cluster with an impressive average score of 87.16, indicating widespread digital connectivity that supports access to data and public services.

Key Obstacles and Gaps

Land management was the lowest-scoring cluster across the Caribbean, which suggests weak governance and lack of transparency in land data. Several indicators scored zero across many countries, including lobbying, land use, political integrity interoperability, and language. These gaps reflect systemic and institutional weaknesses in governance and accountability. The lack of consistent legal and regulatory frameworks, particularly around open data and political finance, continues to hinder progress. Additionally, limited human and financial resources in public sector institutions remain obstacles to implementing and sustaining open data practices.

The Pathway to Strengthening the Caribbean Data Ecosystem

The Global Data Barometer's findings underscore the need for governments in the region to strengthen political commitment and legal frameworks. In the next few years, it is of critical importance for governments to update national open data policies and data protection laws to formalize commitments. In addition, there is

a need for long term investment in capacity building. Continuous training for public servants, civil society, and journalists is essential to ensure data literacy, increase data use, and encourage more informed policymaking, accountability, and transparency.

Land management and political integrity interoperability datasets are some of the lowest ranking datasets in the region. The regional average for political integrity is 22.07, while land management ranks lowest at 3.28. Adopting policies that will improve data collection and publication will go a long way in enhancing transparency and accountability.

As digital literacy improves and citizens become more engaged, we anticipate increased pressure for greater transparency. Many Caribbean governments are expanding e-government services, and we expect that this will likely accelerate data availability. There is no need to reinvent the wheel as countries like the Dominican Republic and Jamaica can serve as examples to other countries in the region that are looking to adopt open data governance.

Although faced with human resources and financial constraints, the Caribbean demonstrates how small, developing states with limited resources can still achieve progress in areas like public procurement and data infrastructure.

While data gaps persist, it is still important to keep having comparable, up-to-date data across the Caribbean.

Reliable and current data informs effective policymaking and development and development strategies. Governments can leverage these insights to address complex issues like inequality. Comparable regional data also supports regional integration, facilitates benchmarking, and enables countries to assess progress, share best practices, and coordinate regional strategies. Most importantly, timely open data strengthens democratic progress in the region by empowering civil society, the media, and citizens to hold public institutions and governments accountable.

Africa

Country	Comparative strength	Comparative weakness	National score
Angola	Availability (CI): Company register	Governance (PI): RTI performance	29.04
Benin	Capability (C): Civil service	Governance (PI): RTI performance	29.97
Botswana	Availability (CI): Company register	Governance (PF): Public finance data	22.78
Burkina Faso	Governance (G): Data management	Governance (CI): Beneficial ownership	27.36
Cameroon	Governance (PF): Public finance data	Governance (G): Data protection	21.48
Cote d'Ivoire	Governance (G): Data protection	Governance (PI): Political finance	25.87
Gambia	Governance (PI): RTI performance	Governance (G): Data protection	21.46
Ghana	Governance (PI): RTI performance	Availability (CI): Company register	36.24
Kenya	Availability (PI): RTI performance data	Availability (CI): Company register	35.91
Liberia	Availability (L): Land tenure	Governance (PP) Public procurement data	14.45
Malawi	Governance (G): Accessibility coverage & data	Governance (PI): RTI performance	26.66
Morocco	Capability (C): Open data initiative	Governance (PI): RTI performance	35.41
Mozambique	Governance (PI): Asset declarations	Governance (G): Data protection	25.90
Namibia	Governance (PI): RTI performance	Governance (G): Data protection	22.10
Nigeria	Governance (G): Open data policy	Governance (PF): Public finance data	35.25
Rwanda	Governance (G): Data protection	Availability (PF): Budget and spend data	30.86
Senegal	Capability (C): Open data initiative	Governance (PI): Political finance	26.82
Sierra Leone	Governance (PI): Political finance	Governance (G): Data protection	19.80
South Africa	Governance (G): Data management	Governance (PI): Asset declarations	47.79
Togo	Availability (CI): Company register	Governance (PF): Public finance data	23.23
Tunisia	Governance (PI): RTI performance	Availability (PF): Budget and spend data	35.67
Uganda	Governance (PI): Political finance	Governance (G): Data management	36.09

Local Development
Research Institute

Hub Perspectives

Local Development Research Institute (Africa)

/Keziah Kithei Munyao

Africa is home to over 50 countries with diverse ethnic, linguistic, cultural, and political identities, yet united by shared aspirations for democratic governance and sustainable development. Each nation carries its own colonial legacy and development path, resulting in a broad spectrum of governance systems and institutional capacities. Despite these differences, the region shares several cross-cutting social and political trends that significantly influence its data landscape and digital transformation efforts.

The Global Data Barometer research covered 22 countries from across Eastern, Central, and Western Africa, as well as parts of the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region. The data landscape across Africa is undergoing a transformative shift, shaped by socio-political change, digital innovation, and growing civic demand for transparency. There is a noticeable uptake in the adoption of legal and institutional frameworks to manage public data responsibly. At the same time, countries are leveraging technology to improve data collection, accessibility, and citizen engagement.

Key Trends in Sub-Saharan Africa

Key upward trends have been noted in Public Procurement, Data Protection,

Budget and Spending Transparency, and Data Infrastructure. These trends highlight growing awareness among African governments of the strategic value of data in driving development, fostering trust, and enhancing accountability. The progress in these areas is often catalyzed by both internal policy reforms and external commitments to initiatives such as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and the Open Government Partnership (OGP). However, gaps remain especially in areas like Political Integrity, Land Management, Lobbying Transparency, and Language. These deficits continue to limit equitable access to information, public oversight, and effective civic participation.

Main Highlights of the Barometer

Public procurement has emerged as a standout area of progress. Several countries have strengthened legal frameworks and decentralized procurement systems to enhance transparency and accountability. While the regional average is 65.48, a closer look reveals that countries like Uganda (92.38), Kenya 88.34, South Africa (87.76) are making strides to effectively govern public procurement processes. Uganda has introduced electronic procurement systems that improve efficiency, reduce corruption, and

promote competitive bidding, while Kenya's Open Contracting Data Standard (OCDS) compliant procurement portal provides real-time, accessible procurement data to the public. These countries offer an example of how comprehensive tracking of public procurement processes can facilitate better public participation, enable scrutiny of government contracts, and enhance value-for-money assessments in public spending.

In addition to public procurement safeguards, countries have taken substantial steps to align national data protection laws with international standards. At least 9 of the 22 countries analyzed have enacted data protection laws, including Kenya, Rwanda, Malawi, and South Africa. However, only a handful show consistent enforcement or have dedicated data protection authorities with operational independence.

Key Obstacles and Challenges

Although data publication is increasing, a widespread lack of public service training continues to undermine data use capacity. Among the 22 countries surveyed, scores varied significantly — some reaching around 50.00, while others fell between 0.00 and 40. This disparity highlights a broader issue: many governments across the continent are not investing adequately in training programs, educational efforts, or targeted capacity-building initiatives needed to translate data into actionable insights.

While progress has been made in establishing supportive legal frameworks for data publication, significant foundational gaps remain across the surveyed countries. Only nine have adopted comprehensive legal frameworks for data management. Addressing these legislative gaps will be critical to enabling meaningful public participation, enhancing governmental transparency, and fostering greater trust in public institutions.

Although all the surveyed countries constitutionally recognize more than one official language, most publish public datasets in only one language. Tunisia is a notable exception, making efforts to provide some datasets in multiple languages. For example, Morocco's 2011 Constitution recognizes Arabic and Amazigh as official languages, and Organic Law No. 26.16 of 2019 supports their integration into public life. However, there is no clear provision requiring government data to be accessible in Amazigh, limiting practical implementation and linguistic inclusivity. This significantly reduces the reach and usability of public data, especially in multilingual societies.

Key Recommendations: Building a Resilient, Inclusive Data Future

While data availability is steadily improving across the region, the capacity to interpret and apply this data effectively remains limited among key stakeholder groups. Bridging the gap between data access and data use requires targeted capacity-building

initiatives, particularly for civil society organizations, journalists, and local government officials. Supporting civic tech hubs, community-driven data programs, and youth-oriented data bootcamps can help democratize data use and spark innovation. Notable examples include Code for Africa's data journalism academies, which equip media practitioners with data analysis skills, and BudgIT's public finance tracking tools in Nigeria, which empower citizens to hold governments accountable.

Legal reforms alone are not enough, effective enforcement is crucial. To bridge this gap, governments must allocate adequate resources to support independent oversight bodies, particularly those responsible for implementing data laws and managing open data platforms. Embedding robust accountability mechanisms within public institutions will be key to translating legal frameworks into meaningful, actionable outcomes.

To ensure that data serves all citizens equitably, especially marginalized groups and persons with disabilities it must be inclusive, accessible, and reflective of diverse realities. An example of inclusive digital infrastructure is the website of [Kenya's Office of the Data Protection Commissioner](#), which has implemented accessibility features to support users with disabilities. This approach reflects a growing recognition that digital inclusion is a key pillar of effective and ethical data governance.

Transparency in political financing, lobbying, and electoral processes is essential for strengthening democratic governance. However, many countries in the region continue to restrict access to politically sensitive datasets, often citing concerns over national stability or political control. Opening up this data is crucial to rebuilding public trust, enhancing civic engagement, and ensuring accountability in government institutions.

Some of the region's most effective data initiatives are rooted in local realities rather than imposed from the top down. Projects such as community mapping, participatory budgeting, and citizen-generated data demonstrate how communities can actively shape the data agenda. For example, OpenStreetMap contributors mapping informal settlements or residents using mobile tools to monitor local budgets reflect how grassroots efforts can fill critical data gaps. Inclusion leads to better data and better outcomes. By anchoring data practices in lived experiences, these initiatives highlight how contextual relevance builds trust, enhances utility, and strengthens impact.

Final Observations

Final Observations

The 2nd Edition of the Global Data Barometer reveals a rapidly changing data environment, marked by both real progress and persistent structural barriers. Across the 43 countries examined by the Barometer, it is clear that there is increasing recognition of the value of data for the public good, signaled by a growing adoption of legal frameworks for data protection and data sharing, and the important strides taken in areas such as public procurement and fiscal transparency. Yet, the findings also highlight deep ongoing gaps in implementation, regional disparities, and an urgent need to shift from policy intent to practical impact.

Data governance remains a critical cornerstone. Where strong governance frameworks are coupled with institutional capacity, data is better managed, used more effectively, and more publicly accessible. However, the advancement of legal and regulatory frameworks is too often undermined by weak enforcement, insufficient investment, and a lack of meaningful inclusion. The risks of fragmented data policies, under-resourced open data programs, and non-interoperable systems are compounded by growing democratic fragility and the expanding role of AI in the public sector.

At the same time, the absence of robust guidance around algorithmic governance and the limitations in AI-related training reflect a broader challenge. As digital technologies evolve, data governance policies and practices must evolve with them. Without deliberate, inclusive, and well-coordinated strategies, the use of data, and AI in particular, risks deepening inequality, entrenching opacity, and eroding public trust.

Moving forward, governments, civil society, and international actors must work together to reframe data not merely as a technical or economic asset, but as a foundation for democratic renewal, social equity, and ethical innovation. This will require:

- Closing the implementation gap by investing in critical data competencies.
- Prioritizing inclusion by increasing data accessibility and multilingual publication.
- Institutionalizing interoperability across sectors and datasets.
- Embedding AI governance within broader data strategies.

The Global Data Barometer offers a practical evidence base to guide these efforts. More than that, it calls for a renewed collective commitment to building data ecosystems that are transparent, rights-respecting, and grounded in the public interest. In an era of uncertainty and opportunity, such systems are not just desirable—they are essential.

We invite governments, civil society organizations, researchers, and international partners to engage with the findings of the 2nd Edition and use them to inform action. Whether that means investing in data literacy, reforming regulatory frameworks, supporting open data ecosystems, or advancing responsible AI governance, the time to act is now. The Global Data Barometer is not just a diagnostic. It is a shared platform for collaboration, accountability, and progress. By working together to close gaps, amplify what works, and foreground equity in data systems, we can build the foundations of a healthier digital future.

| Annexes

Annex 1-Scoring Methodology

This appendix contains details of the weightings applied for the calculation of the Global Data Barometer scores. More details on the survey methodology used for data collection can be found in the [research handbook](#) or this report's Methodology chapter which is not reproduced here.

Score Structure

The Barometer is structured around three pillars and is composed of 27 primary indicators from an expert survey and 12 secondary indicators.

In this 2nd edition, the scoring methodology is updated to simplify and standardise the process. Unlike in the 1st edition, we no longer calculate the country score by first producing pillar scores and then aggregating them. Instead, we now calculate it directly from indicator scores.

As previously mentioned in this report's Methodology chapter, the 2nd edition organizes indicators into **action areas** and **clusters**. The Barometer now produces the following scores at different levels but all directly from indicator scores:

- **National Score:** Weight average of all indicator scores.
 - ◊ **Cluster Score:** Weight average of all associated indicator scores.
 - » **Action Area Score:** Weighted average of all associated indicator scores.
 - ✓ **Indicator Score:** Primary indicator (Multiplier * Element Score);
Secondary indicator (secondary source normalized score).

For each of primary indicator, the score is calculated based upon two components, as stated:

- **Element Score:** it is derived from the responses to the Element's sub-questions from the expert survey, combined with fixed weights assigned to each sub-questions.

- **Multiplier:** By combining the responses to the Existence and Extent sub-questions, we calculate a single multiplier to adjust the Element Score, resulting in the final Indicator Score.

For the weight assigned to indicators to calculate the action areas scores, clusters scores and the national scores, please refer to the Annexes: Indicators for detailed breakdown.

Element scoring and weights

The element section of each indicator is initially scored on a range from 0 to 100, as a result of weighted sum of all element sub-questions.

The element section is divided into subgroups (e1, e2 & e3). Within the subgroups, sub-questions are generally equally weighted with minor adjustments on theoretical grounds. The weight of each group is set based on the question justification and seeks to balance the relative importance of the sub-questions to an overall evaluation of the indicator drawing on established frameworks and precedent, as well as supporting comparability between indicators. For example, in Availability indicators, upwards of 60% of the element score is made up from a common checklist of properties of the surveyed dataset (such as machine readable, openly licensed and updated); while around 40% of the score comes from dataset specific elements (such as approved budget, amended budget and budget spending in the Public Finance Indicator). For detailed weights, please refer to the weight column in the Barometer dataset.

Two special subgroups exist within specific indicators. The first subgroup is called “Negative Scoring” (labelled ‘eb’ in the GDB identifier), generally removing points from the total element score when responses indicate ‘Yes’ or ‘Partially’. There are two “Negative Scoring” questions in the second edition: the ‘MISSINGDATA’ question in all Availability indicators, and the ‘DPLEXCEPTIONS’ in the “Governance (G): Data protection” indicator. Each of these questions can remove up to 10 points from the total 100 element score.

The other special subgroup is “Nonscoring” (labelled ‘eu’), which is not scored. This subgroup exists in all Availability indicators, with all having the ‘DATA_USE’ sub-question and only three indicators having the ‘GENDER’ sub-question.

In the second edition, all sub-questions in the element section are standardized to be 3-option questions, which can be answered with ‘Yes’ (1), ‘Partially’ (0.5) or ‘No’ (0). The research handbook provides general guidance on when to use the partially response, and specific guidance is provided for certain sub-questions (detailed in the handbook).

Finding sub-question weights

All the question weights used can be found in the published Barometer dataset (Available at <https://www.globaldatabarometer.org>) which contains a number of key fields that combined show the weights that have been applied. To find the weight of each sub-question:

- Filter on the hlevel column to hlevel=4 (hierarchy level = 4 = sub-questions)
- Filter on the data_type column to data_type='response' (to see responses rather than summaries, supporting data, or other content). Weights can then be read from the following fields:

field	description
response	The answer selected or entered by the researcher. For data_type='response'
response_value	This will generally be a fixed option provided by the survey. The numeric value assigned to the score. For questions with ‘No’ (0), ‘Partially’ (1), ‘Yes’ (2) answers this will be in the range 0-2. For some Existence and Extent questions this can range 0-3.
normalized_response_value	Each score is re-scaled on a 0-1 scale
weight	A multiplier applied to the calculated score to get the weighted contribution of this question to the indicator. With minimal exceptions, sub-question weights are held constant within the same subsection of the indicator.
score	normalizad_response_value*weight

Worked example

The following example shows the elements for the “Governance (G): Data protection” indicator assessing “To what extent do relevant laws, regulations, policies, and guidance provide a comprehensive framework for protection of personal data?”.

GDB Identifier	Sub-question	Weight	Notes
G.GOVERNANCE.DPL.e	Elements	100	The highest score on all elements would sum to 100
G.GOVERNANCE.DPL.e.e1	Rights and responsibilities:	80	For this indicator the e1 element group is worth 80 of the 100 points available. There are five elements in this group, so each is worth 16 points.
G.GOVERNANCE.DPL.e.e1.ACCESS_CORRECTION	Elements Question 1: The framework provides data subjects with rights to access and correct data about themselves.	16	
G.GOVERNANCE.DPL.e.e1.REDRESS	Elements Question 2: The framework provides rights of redress.	16	
G.GOVERNANCE.DPL.e.e1.CONSENT	Elements Question 3: The framework provides data subjects with rights of choice or consent.	16	
G.GOVERNANCE.DPL.e.e1.DATA_HOLDER_RESPONSIBILITY	Elements Question 4: The framework sets out clear responsibilities for data holders.	16	
G.GOVERNANCE.DPL.e.e1.BREACH	Elements Question 5: The framework requires data controllers to notify an appropriate authority of data breaches.	16	
G.GOVERNANCE.DPL.e.e2	Specific considerations:	20	For this indicator, the e2 element group is worth 20 out of the 100 points available. There are three elements in this group, so each is worth 6.66(7) points.

G.GOVERNANCE.DPL.e.e2.GROUPPRIVACY	Elements Question 6: The framework explicitly addresses privacy and data protection for groups.	6.67	
G.GOVERNANCE.DPL.e.e2.LOCATION	Elements Question 7: The framework explicitly covers the protection of location-related data.	6.67	
G.GOVERNANCE.DPL.e.e2.AI	Elements Question 8: The framework addresses algorithmic decision-making.	6.66	
G.GOVERNANCE.DPL.e.eb	Negative scoring:	-10	For this indicator, the eb element group can remove up to 10 points from the score gained
G.GOVERNANCE.DPL.e.eb.DPLEXCEPTIONS	Elements Question 9: The framework excludes certain populations from data protection.	-10	

If we imagine a country where the researcher answers ‘Yes’ to CONSENT (1 (score) x (weight) 16), ACCESS_CORRECTION (1 x 16) and DATA_HOLDER_RESPONSIBILITY (1 x 16), ‘Partially’ to REDRESS (0.5 x 16), BREACH (0.5 x 16) and LOCATION (0.5 x 6.66) and DPLEXCEPTIONS (0.5 x -10), and ‘No’ to AI (0 x 6.66) and GROUPPRIVACY (0 x 6.67), then we would calculate the element score as 62.33.

Existence Multiplier

A single multiplier is derived from the existence section of the indicator, which is typically composed of two distinct question types: (1) EXIST questions, which is usually denoted by variables prefixed with "EXIST", and (2) EXTENT questions, which is moved into the EXISTENCE section in the second edition with variables usually prefixed with "EXTENT". Note that the quantity of these questions varies across indicators, with 1 or 2 instances per indicator. Each set of EXIST and EXTENT questions independently generates a multiplier, denoted as Multiplier_Exist and Multiplier_Extent, respectively (we discuss how they are calculated in details below). Then, the final single multiplier is calculated as the product of these two components.

Multiplier= Normalization(Multiplier_Exist * Multiplier_Extent)

$$\text{Normalization (x)} = 0.6 + \frac{(x - \text{min})}{(\text{max} - \text{min})} * 0.4$$

Note that the final calculation step applies normalization to the interval [0.6–1.0], triggered exclusively when any country's multiplier falls below 0.6. This protocol mitigates multi-level cascading effects from layered calculations, ensuring computational integrity while maintaining score relativity.

Regarding the computation of the Multiplier_Exist and Multiplier_Extent, different approaches are taken in the different pillars of the Barometer:

Multiplier_Exist

It takes three steps to calculate the Multiplier_Exist:

Step 1: Normalize the Response value

The first step involves converting survey response options to a standardized [0, 1] scale. In the 2nd edition, most indicators use three-option existence questions (e.g., No, Partially, Yes), which are assigned numeric values of 0, 1, and 2 during data collection. These values are normalized to 0, 0.5, and 1, respectively.

A single exception applies to the Capability pillar indicators, which include a four-option exist question. These responses are assigned numeric values of 0, 1, 2, and 3, then normalized to 0, 0.333, 0.666, and 1 to maintain a proportional [0, 1] scale.

Note for “Governance (G): Accessibility coverage & data” indicator, special handling is applied. The original EXIST_ACCESS question is not directly used in calculations. Instead, the computed variable EXIST_ACCESS_LEVEL is employed. This variable represents a new data point created by the GDB team during the review process, where evidence was systematically classified based on standardized evidence criteria. EXIST_ACCESS_LEVEL is included in the published GDB dataset and replaces the original question for scoring purposes.

Step 2: Combine Multiple Existence if necessary

In the 2nd edition, only the governance indicators within the thematic cluster (e.g. the Governance (PI): RTI framework indicator) have two exist questions.

The two exist questions are EXIST_COLLECTION and EXIST_PUBLICATION. Their answers shall be combined together to be a single answer before proceeding by following the below rules:

- Operational: both are operational
- Weak Operational: one is "Yes" (operational) and the other is not
- Draft: both are draft, or one is draft and the other is not operational
- No: both are No

Step 3: Look up the table for Multiplier_Exist value

Look up the Multiplier value in the corresponding table below based on the indicator type.

Availability indicators:

Normalized Value	Multiplier Value
0 (data not online)	0
0.5 (data online as non-gov action)	0.5
1 (data online as a gov-action)	1

Governance Indicators (non-thematic, excluding the Accessibility indicator):

Normalized Value	Multiplier Value
0 (no framework)	0
0.5 (not full force of law)	0.9
1 (force of law)	1

Governance indicators (thematic):

Combined Existence	Multiplier_Existence
0 (not exist)	0
0.5 (framework is draft)	0.6
0.75 (framework is weak operational)	0.8
1 (framework is operational)	1

Capabilities indicators and the Accessibility Indicator (Governance Pillar):

Normalized Value	Multiplier Value
0	0
0.333	0.6
0.666	0.8
1	1

Multiplier_Extent

Similarly, it also takes 3 steps to calculate the Multiplier_Extent:

Step 1: Normalize the Response

It is normalized using the same method as the Multiplier_Exist described above.

Step 2: Combine multiple Extents

Extent questions in the 2nd edition are categorized into two types:

(1) Flow Stopper Extent

It typically assesses whether data or frameworks have national or representative coverage.

If the flow stopper extent receives a No-equivalent response (e.g., "No coverage"), the entire combined extent value is set to 0, as this halts the questionnaire flow, rendering subsequent element questions inapplicable.

Note that "Availability (L): Land tenure" indicator contains two special extent questions whose variables are 'LAND_URBAN' and 'LAND_

RURAL'. These two questions assess whether the data covers urban land and rural land. The two shall be combined and treated as a single extent, and only when both of them receive a No answer, then the survey flow gets stopped.

(2) Non-Flow Stopper Extent:

It typically evaluates coverage of government agencies or sector-specific domains. A No-equivalent response here does not override the combined EXTENT value. Thus, the survey flow doesn't stop.

When multiple Extent values are combined, their normalized values are summed. However, as noted earlier, if a flow stopper extent receives a No-equivalent response (e.g., "No" or equivalent normalized value of 0), the combined extent result is automatically set to 0, overriding any summed values.

Step 3: Multiplier value

Depending on how many Extents questions in an indicator, the rule to map the response value to multiplier value is slightly different.

1. Single Extent: It is always the flow stopper and note here the "Availability (L): Land tenure" indicator's two extent questions are combined and considered as a single extent.

Extent normalized value	Multiplier Value
0	0
0.5	0.85
1	1

2. Multiple Extent: the maximum number of extent questions is two in the second edition. And normally one is flow stopper and the other is not, then the following rules are applied:

Extent normalized value	Multiplier Value
0	0
0.5	0.7
1	0.85
1.5	0.9
2	1

Worked example

The following calculation is based upon the “Governance (PI): RTI performance” indicator assessing “To what extent do relevant laws, regulations, policies, and guidance provide a basis for collecting and publishing data on the performance of right to information (RTI) / freedom of information (FOI) processes?”

The indicator contains:

- Two exist questions asking the requirements on collection and publication of the RTI performance information
- Two extent questions:
 - ◊ The flow stopper extent asking how comprehensive, in terms of jurisdiction, is the coverage of the framework assessed for this question?
 - ◊ The non-flow stopper extent asking how comprehensive, in terms of parts of government, is the framework assessed for this question?

Let us imagine country A with an operational collection framework (Yes=1) but no publication framework (No=0). Its combined existence thus shall be weak operational (0.75) and the Multiplier_Exist is 0.8. And its framework covers the whole nation (Yes=1) but only limited parts of governments (No-equivalent=0), then the Multiplier_Extent is 0.85 (as the combined extent is 1). if there is no country with a multiplier being lower than 0.6, then the multiplier for this country is 0.68.

However, if there is a country B with only draft frameworks (Multiplier_Exist = 0.6) and the same extent answers (Multiplier_Extent = 0.85), then its multiplier is lower than 0.6 (0.51). This will trigger the normalization process. Let us assume the lowest multiplier is 0.51, and the highest multiplier is 1, then the normalized multiplier of country A shall be 0.74, and the normalized multiplier of country B shall be 0.6.

Indicators

Indicator Sources and Weights

The 2nd edition includes 27 primary indicators and 12 secondary indicators. In this section, indicators are organized by clusters with their action area, question/source, and weights information listed for reference.

Cluster: Governance foundations

Action Area	Indicator Type	Indicator Name	Question/Source	WiB	WiAA	WiC
Data protection	Primary Indicator	Governance (G): Data protection	To what extent do relevant laws, regulations, policies, and guidance provide a comprehensive framework for protection of personal data?	0.0334	1.0000	0.1843
Data management	Primary Indicator	Governance (G): Data management	To what extent do relevant laws, regulations, policies, and guidance provide a comprehensive framework for consistent data management and publication?	0.0334	1.0000	0.1843
Data sharing	Primary Indicator	Governance (G): Data sharing frameworks	To what extent do relevant laws, regulations, policies, and guidance provide a comprehensive framework for data sharing?	0.0334	1.0000	0.1843
Data Infrastructure	Secondary Indicator	Capability (C): Government online services	UN E-Government Survey: UN eGov Online Service Index (2020)	0.0170	0.2098	0.0938
Data Infrastructure	Secondary Indicator	Capability (C): Digital Government	World Bank-DGSS dataset: Is there a DG/GovTech Strategy?; Is there a dedicated GovTech institution; Is there a national strategy on disruptive technologies?; Is there a government cloud (shared platform)?; Is there a government service bus / interoperability platform in place?	0.0170	0.2098	0.0938

Action Area	Indicator Type	Indicator Name	Question/Source	WiB	WiAA	WiC
Data	Secondary Indicator	Governance (G): Data protection	International Telecommunication Union (ITU): Fixed broad-band basket as a % of GNI p.c; Individuals using the Inter-net, total (%)	0.0100	0.1235	0.0552
Data	Secondary Indicator	Capability (C): Data institutions	World Bank-DGSS dataset: Is there a government entity in charge of data governance or data management?, Is there a data protection authority?	0.0100	0.1236	0.0553
Data	Secondary Indicator	Capability (C): Political freedoms and civil liberties	FreedomHouse: Political Rights score & Civil Liberties (score)	0.0170	0.2068	0.0938
Data	Secondary Indicator	Capability (C): Use of standards and methods in statistic offices	Statistical Performance Indicators: Dimension 5.2: Standards and Methods	0.0100	0.1235	0.0552

Cluster: Critical competencies

Action Area	Indicator Type	Indicator Name	Question/Source	WiB	WiAA	WiC
Data literacy	Primary Indicator	Capability (C): Civil service	To what extent is the government providing training to develop civil servants' data literacy and data skills?	0.0334	0.5529	0.1752
Data literacy	Secondary Indicator	Capability (C): Human capital	UN E-Government Survey: UN eGov Human Capital Index	0.017	0.2815	0.0892
Data literacy	Secondary Indicator	Capability (C): Digital skills	WE Forum Executive Opinion Survey: Skill levels of the workforce: Technology skills	0.01	0.1656	0.0525

Action Area	Indicator Type	Indicator Name	Question/Source	WiB	WiAA	WiC
Data reuse	Primary Indicator	Capability (C): Government support for re-use	To what extent is there evidence that the government is providing support for data reuse?	0.0334	0.2565	0.1752
Data reuse	Primary Indicator	Governance (G): Open data policy	To what extent do relevant laws, regulations, policies, and guidance provide a comprehensive framework for generating and publishing open data?	0.0334	0.2566	0.1752
Data reuse	Primary Indicator	Capability (C): Open data initiative	To what extent is there a well-resourced open government data initiative in the country?	0.0334	0.2565	0.1752
Data reuse	Secondary Indicator	Capability (C): Data use by international organizations	Statistical Performance Indicators: Dimension 1.5: Data use by international organizations	0.01	0.0768	0.0525
Data reuse	Secondary Indicator	Capability (C): Knowledge-intensive employment	Global Innovation Index / ILO: Employment in knowledge-intensive occupations (% of workforce)	0.01	0.0768	0.0525
Data reuse	Secondary Indicator	Capability (C): AI Adoption by Business	WE Forum Executive Opinion Survey: combine "Adoption of AI among local businesses: new products and business models" and "Adoption of AI among local businesses: enhance productivity"	0.01	0.0768	0.0525

Cluster: Equitable access

Note that the indicator “Governance (G): Language coverage & data” is not included in calculating any higher-level scores, because post-survey checks on data quality suggested that responses were not robust enough to rely on. However, we still score it at the indicator level to provide quantitative data alongside qualitative data for further analysis.

Action Area	Indicator Type	Indicator Name	Question/Source	WiB	WiAA	WiC
Language	Primary Indicator	Governance (G): Language coverage & data	To what extent do relevant laws, regulations, policies, and guidance ensure linguistic inclusion with regard to data?	0.0000	1.0000	0.0000
Accessibility	Primary Indicator	Governance (G): Accessibility coverage & data	To what extent do relevant laws, regulations, policies, and guidance ensure the inclusion of people with disabilities with regard to data?	0.0334	1.0000	1.0000

Cluster: Company information

Action Area	Indicator Type	Indicator Name	Question/Source	WiB	WiAA	WiC
Company register	Primary Indicator	Availability (CI): Company register	To what extent is detailed company information available for public use?	0.0321	1	0.3333
Beneficial ownership of companies	Primary Indicator	Governance (CI): Beneficial ownership	To what extent do relevant laws, regulations, policies, and guidance provide a basis for collecting and publishing data on the beneficial ownership of companies?	0.0321	0.5	0.3334
Beneficial ownership of companies	Primary Indicator	Availability (CI): Beneficial ownership	To what extent is detailed information about the beneficial ownership of companies available for public use?	0.0321	0.5	0.3333

Cluster: Land Management

Action Area	Indicator Type	Indicator Name	Question/Source	WiB	WiAA	WiC
Land tenure	Primary Indicator	Availability (L): Land tenure	To what extent is detailed land tenure information available as open data?	0.0321	1	0.5
Land use	Primary Indicator	Availability (L): Existing land use	To what extent is existing land use information available as open data?	0.0321	1	0.5

Cluster: Political integrity

Action Area	Indicator Type	Indicator Name	Question/Source	WiB	WiAA	WiC
Political finance	Primary Indicator	Governance (PI): Political finance	To what extent do relevant laws, regulations, policies, and guidance provide a basis for collecting and publishing data on campaign and party finance?	0.0321	0.5	0.1049
Political finance	Primary Indicator	Availability (PI): Political finance data	To what extent is detailed political finance information available for public use?	0.0321	0.5	0.105
Interest and asset declarations	Primary Indicator	Governance (PI): Asset declarations	To what extent do relevant laws, regulations, policies, and guidance provide a basis for collecting and publishing data on the interests and assets of public officials?	0.0321	0.5	0.1049
Interest and asset declarations	Primary Indicator	Availability (PI): Asset declarations	To what extent is detailed interest and asset declaration information available for public use?	0.0321	0.5	0.105

Action Area	Indicator Type	Indicator Name	Question/Source	WiB	WiAA	WiC
Lobbying	Primary Indicator	Governance (PI): Lobbying register	To what extent do relevant laws, regulations, policies, and guidance provide a basis for collecting and publishing data on lobbying activities?	0.0321	0.5	0.1049
Lobbying	Primary Indicator	Availability (PI): Lobbying data	To what extent is detailed lobbying information available for public use?	0.0321	0.5	0.1049
RTI performance	Primary Indicator	Governance (PI): RTI performance	To what extent do relevant laws, regulations, policies, and guidance provide a basis for collecting and publishing data on the performance of right to information (RTI) / freedom of information (FOI) processes?	0.0321	0.3953	0.1049
RTI performance	Primary Indicator	Availability (PI): RTI performance data	To what extent is detailed RTI performance information available for public use?	0.0321	0.3953	0.105
RTI performance	Secondary Indicator	Governance (PI): RTI framework	RTI Rating: RTI Rating	0.0170	0.2094	0.0556
Political integrity interoperability	Primary Indicator	Capability (PI): Political integrity interoperability	To what extent is political integrity data interoperable across different political integrity datasets, as well as other datasets associated with relevant information flows?	0.0321	1	0.1049

Cluster: Public finance

Action Area	Indicator Type	Indicator Name	Question/Source	WiB	WiAA	WiC
Budget and spending	Primary Indicator	Governance (PF): Public finance data	To what extent do relevant laws, regulations, policies, and guidance provide a basis for collecting and publishing data on public finances? (E.g., government budgets, government spending, debt, and borrowing.)	0.0321	0.5	0.5
Budget and spending	Primary Indicator	Availability (PF): Budget and spend data	To what extent is detailed government budget and spending information (budget execution) available for public use?	0.0321	0.5	0.5

Cluster: Public procurement

Action Area	Indicator Type	Indicator Name	Question/Source	WiB	WiAA	WiC
Public procurement	Primary Indicator	Governance (PP) Public procurement data	To what extent do relevant laws, regulations, policies, and guidance provide a basis for collecting and publishing data on government procurement?	0.0321	0.5	0.5
Public procurement	Primary Indicator	Availability (PP): Public procurement data	To what extent is detailed public procurement information available for public use?	0.0321	0.5	0.5

Changes to the Indicators in the GDB 2nd Edition

This section presents the changes to indicators in the 2nd edition compared to the 1st edition, including added/removed indicators, questions added/removed/split within related indicators, and variable modifications to questions in related indicators.

Added or Removed Indicators

GDB 1st Edition	Adjustments	GDB 2nd Edition
Capability (C): Digital skills	<p>Source Changed</p> <p>This secondary indicator was originally derived from the World Economic Forum Executive Opinion Survey's indicator "Digital skills among active population" (score) . However, the WE Forum has discontinued this historical measure and transitioned to a new indicator "Skill levels of the workforce: Technology skills", which now forms the basis for this secondary indicator's calculation.</p>	Capability (C): Digital skills
Capability (C): Business use of digital tools	<p>Removed</p> <p>This secondary indicator was originally derived from the World Economic Forum Executive Opinion Survey's indicator "Business use of digital tools" (score), which has been discontinued and there are no similar indicators from the WE Forum to provide similar measurement.</p>	Governance (G): Accessibility coverage & data

	<p>New Indicator</p> <p>This secondary indicator is derived from the World Economic Forum Executive Opinion Survey's indicators: "Adoption of AI among local businesses: new products and business models" and "Adoption of AI among local businesses: enhance productivity". This new indicator addresses the measurement gap created by the retirement of the "Capability (C): Business Use of Digital Tools" indicator, enabling continued benchmarking of business capability in data utilization.</p>	Capability (C): AI Adoption by Business
Use (U): Data use by international organizations	<p>Name Changed</p> <p>As in the 2nd edition there is no longer a Use pillar, this secondary indicator is now moved into the Capability pillar.</p>	Capability (C): Data use by international organizations
Governance (G): Language coverage & data	<p>Methodology Changed</p> <p>The primary indicator's main question has been redesigned, evolving from "To what extent do relevant laws, regulations, policies, and guidance require that data collection and publication processes be available in the country's official or national languages? If the country has no official or national languages, are these processes available in the languages used in the country? " (1st edition) to "To what extent do relevant laws, regulations, policies, and guidance ensure linguistic inclusion with regard to data?"(2nd edition).</p> <p>For detailed question-level changes, please refer to the research handbook</p>	Governance (G): Language coverage & data

Governance (G): Accessibility coverage & data	<p>Methodology Changed</p> <p>The primary indicator's main question has been redesigned, evolving from "To what extent do relevant laws, regulations, policies, and guidance require that data collection and publication be accessible to people with disabilities? " (1st edition) to "To what extent do relevant laws, regulations, policies, and guidance ensure the inclusion of people with disabilities with regard to data??"(2nd edition).</p> <p>For detailed question-level changes, please refer to the W</p>	Governance (G): Accessibility coverage & data
	<p>New Indicator</p> <p>This new primary indicator is introduced to be paired with the existing indicator "Availability (PP): Public procurement data", enabling investigation of implementation gaps with regard to procurement data.</p>	Governance (PP) Public procurement data

Changes to sub-questions: Cross-Indicator

In the 2nd edition, we added or replaced questions recurring across multiple indicators. The table below summarizes all changes. Note: "Question Variable" refers to the last part of the GDB identifier (referred as "variable_name" in 1st edition dataset). For example, the question "SUM_EXISTENCE" appears in both the indicator "Availability (CI): Company register" as "A.COMPANY.REG.a.SUM_EXISTENCE" and the indicator "Governance (G): Data protection" as "G.GOVERNANCE.DPL.a.SUM_EXISTENCE".

Question Variable (the last part of the GDB Identifier)	Change Type	Adjustment	Impacted Indicators
SUM_EXISTENCE	New Question	<p>The new question is added as the last question of the Existence section.</p> <p>The question text is "Please summarize your answers to the preceding existence sub-questions, including the extent of existence."</p>	All primary Indicators
SUM_ELEMENTS	New Question	<p>The new question is added as the last question of the Element section.</p> <p>The question text is: "Please summarize your answers to the preceding element sub-questions."</p>	All primary Indicators
EXIST_PUBLICATION	Split	<p>The 1st edition variable is 'EXIST' and its original question is "Are there laws, policies, or regulations requiring collection or publication of this information in any form?"</p> <p>Now the question is split into two questions, and this question on collection asks "Are there laws, policies, or regulations requiring publication of this information in any form?"</p>	All thematic governance indicators

EXIST_COLLECTION	Split	The 1st edition variable is 'EXIST' and its original question is "Are there laws, policies, or regulations requiring collection or publication of this information in any form?"	All thematic governance indicators
DATARULES	Removed	The question in the 1st edition originally asks "Do relevant laws, policies, regulations, or guidance discuss the publication of open data?" It is discontinued in the 2nd edition to avoid confusing researchers how to proceed with element questions. However, the new elements sub-question on public access includes a supporting question for matching across editions.	All thematic governance indicators
PUBLIC_ACCESS	New Question	The new question is added into the Element's subgroup "Provisions for collection and access" The question text is: "The framework discusses public access to the data."	Governance (CI): Beneficial ownership Governance (PI): Political finance Governance (PI): Lobbying register Governance (PI): RTI performance Governance (PF): Public finance data Governance (PP) Public procurement data

DIGITAL_COL	Replaced	<p>This new question replaces the 1st edition's question STRUCTURED, whose question text is "The rules/guidance support the collection of structured data."</p> <p>The question text is: "The framework supports the digital collection of data."</p> <p>To maintain a point of continuity with the 1st edition data, the question has a supporting question that asks, in the event of a "Partially" or "Yes" answer, "Does the framework support the collection of structured data? Please explain your response."</p>	All thematic governance indicators
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Changes to sub-questions: Specific-Indicator

The below table summarises all changes to questions of specific indicators. Note here we use the GDB identifier to refer to the specific question of a specific indicator, which you can use to locate the question directly in the second edition's open data.

Indicator	GDB Identifier	Change Type	Adjustment
Availability (CI): Company register	A.COMPANY.REG.e.e1. SHAREHOLDERS	New Question	<p>The new question is added into the Element subgroup "Data fields and specifics".</p> <p>The question text is: "The data contains details of each shareholder, including names, number of shares, and category of shares."</p>

Governance (CI): Beneficial ownership	G.COMPANY.BOT.e.e1. DEFN-BENEFIT	New Question	The new question is added into the Element subgroup "Provisions for definitions, kinds, and fields". The question text is: "Definitions cover "benefiting from"."
Governance (PI): Political finance	G.PI.POLFIN.e.e1. DEFINITIONS_PARTY	Split Question	The original question "DEFINITIONS" in the 1st edition has been split into three sub-questions. The question text is:"The framework contains clear and unambiguous definitions of what constitutes campaigning activities for political parties."
Governance (PI): Political finance	G.PI.POLFIN.e.e1. DEFINITIONS_CANDIDATES	Split Question	The original question "DEFINITIONS" in the 1st edition has been split into three sub-questions. The question text is:"The framework contains clear and unambiguous definitions of what constitutes campaigning activities for candidates."
Governance (PI): Political finance	G.PI.POLFIN.e.e1. DEFINITIONS_THIRDPARTY	Split Question	The original question "DEFINITIONS" in the 1st edition has been split into three sub-questions. The question text is:"The framework contains clear and unambiguous definitions of what constitutes campaigning activities for third parties (i.e., non-contestants who seek to influence the election result)."
Governance (PI): Political finance	G.PI.POLFIN.e.e1. STATERESOURCES	New Question	The new question is added into the Element subgroup "Provisions for definitions, kinds, and fields". The question text is: "The framework requires collecting specific information on the use of state resources for campaigning."

Availability (PI): Political finance data	A.PI.POLFIN.e.e1. THIRDPARTY	New Question	The new question is added into the Element subgroup "Data fields and specifics (II)". The question text is: "The data contains details of donations to third parties."
Availability (PI): Political finance data	A.PI.POLFIN.e.e2. THIRDPARTY	New Question	The new question is added into the Element subgroup "Data fields and specifics (II)". The question text is: "The data contains details of donations to third parties."
Governance (PI): Asset declarations	G.PI.IAD.e.e1. NONFINANCIAL	Replaced	The original question 'INKIND' in the 1st edition has been replaced. The question text is: "The framework requires collecting specific information on interests, assets, and liabilities."
Governance (PI): Asset declarations	G.PI.IAD.e.e3.ADHOC	New Question	The new question is added into the Element subgroup "Provisions for collection and access". The question text is: "The framework requires that data is updated ad hoc to disclose emergent conflicts of interest."
Availability (PI): Asset declarations	A.PI.IAD.e.e1. NONFINANCIAL	New Question	The new question is added into the Element subgroup "Data fields and specifics". The question text is: "The data contains information on non-financial interests."
Capability (PI): Political integrity interoperability	C.PI.INTEROP.e.e1. COMMONID	Removed	The original question text is: "The key datasets for this theme share common identifiers that facilitate mapping flows across the data ecosystem." The question is removed due to substantive overlap with the extent sub-question.

Capability (PI): Political integrity interoperability	C.PI.INTEROP.e.e1. REGULATIONS	Removed	<p>The original question text is: "Lobbying registers and public consultation data use common identifiers for regulations."</p> <p>The question is removed due to the discontinuation of the Public Consultation indicators</p>
Capability (PI): Political integrity interoperability	C.PI.INTEROP.e.e2.LAND	Removed	<p>The original question text is: "The key datasets for the political integrity and land modules share common identifiers that facilitate mapping flows across the data ecosystem."</p> <p>The question is temporarily removed in the 2nd edition due to the fact that land indicators data are separately collected by thematic partner, the Land Portal.</p>
Availability (L): Land tenure	A.LAND.TENURE.a.LAND_ URBAN	Split Question	<p>The original question "EXTENT" in the 1st edition has been split into two sub-questions.</p> <p>The question text is: "Do the datasets available cover the majority of urban land tenure?"</p>
Availability (L): Land tenure	A.LAND.TENURE.a.LAND_ RURAL	Split Question	<p>The original question "EXTENT" in the 1st edition has been split into two sub-questions.</p> <p>The question text is: "Do the datasets available cover the majority of rural land tenure?"</p>
Availability (L): Land tenure	A.LAND.TENURE.e.e1. UTILITIES	New Question	<p>The new question is added into the Element subgroup "Kinds of data"</p> <p>The question text is: "The data contains information about roads, utilities, and corresponding rights."</p>

Availability (L): Land tenure	A.LAND.TENURE.e.e1. MINERAL	New Question	The new question is added into the Element subgroup "Kinds of data" The question text is:"The data contains information about geological/mineral resources and rights."
Availability (L): Land tenure	A.LAND.TENURE.e.e1. NATURAL	New Question	The new question is added into the Element subgroup "Kinds of data" The question text is:"The data contains information about natural resources and environmental mapping/rights."
Availability (L): Existing land use	A.LAND.ELU.e.e1.FOREST	Removed	The original question text is:"Forested areas can be identified in available data or in a related dataset."
Availability (L): Existing land use	A.LAND.ELU.e.e1. PROTECTEDAREAS	Removed	The original question text is:"Protected areas can be identified in available data or in a related dataset."
Availability (L): Existing land use	A.LAND.ELU.e.e1.PUBLIC	New Question	A new Element subgroup is introduced in the 2nd edition, which is called "Kinds of data" and the question is added into this group. The question text is:"Data is available on uses of public land."
Availability (L): Existing land use	A.LAND.ELU.e.e1. NONPUBLIC	New Question	A new Element subgroup is introduced in the 2nd edition, which is called "Kinds of data" and the question is added into this group. The question text is:"Data is available on uses of non-public land."

Availability (L): Existing land use	A.LAND.ELU.e.e1. ENFORCEMENT	New Question	A new Element subgroup is introduced in the 2nd edition, which is called "Kinds of data" and the question is added into this group. The question text is:"Data is available on enforcement of land use zoning."
Governance (G): Data protection	G.GOVERNANCE.DPL.e.e2. GROUPPRIVACY	New Question	The new question is added into the Element subgroup "Specific considerations." The question text is:"The framework explicitly addresses privacy and data protection for groups."
Governance (G): Data protection	G.GOVERNANCE.DPL.e.eb. DPLEXCEPTIONS	New Question	The new question is added into the Element subgroup "Negative Scoring" The question text is:"The framework excludes certain populations from data protection."
Governance (G): Data protection	G.GOVERNANCE.DPL.e.eb. COVIDEXCEPTIONS	Removed	The original question text is:"Exceptions to the usual data protection framework have been made as part of the country's COVID-19 response." Given the adapted state of public health around the world, this is no longer asked
Governance (G): Data sharing frameworks	G.GOVERNANCE. DATASHARING.e.e2. ACCOUNTABILITY	New Question	The new question is added into the Element subgroup "Rights and responsibilities" The question text is:"The framework establishes unambiguously who is accountable at each step of data sharing, including resharing."

Governance (G): Data sharing frameworks	G.GOVERNANCE.DATASHARING.e.e2.OVERSIGHT	New Question	The new question is added into the Element subgroup "Rights and responsibilities" The question text is:"The framework establishes oversight mechanisms for every step of data sharing, including resharing.."
Governance (G): Data sharing frameworks	G.GOVERNANCE.DATASHARING.e.e2.IMPACTASSESS	New Question	The new question is added into the Element subgroup "Rights and responsibilities" The question text is:"The framework requires an impact assessment to be carried out before data is shared."
Governance (G): Data sharing frameworks	G.GOVERNANCE.DATASHARING.e.e2.PORTABILITY	New Question	The new question is added into the Element subgroup "Rights and responsibilities" The question text is:"The framework establishes rights to data portability."
Governance (G): Data sharing frameworks	G.GOVERNANCE.DATASHARING.e.e3.PUBLICINTEREST	New Question	The new question is added into the Element subgroup "Specific considerations" The question text is:"The framework requires certain private sector data to be shared in the public interest."
Governance (G): Data sharing frameworks	G.GOVERNANCE.DATASHARING.e.e3.SALE	New Question	The new question is added into the Element subgroup "Specific considerations" The question text is:"The framework restricts data brokers' ability to sell or exchange detailed personal information."
Capability (C): Civil service	C.CAPABILITIES.TRAIN.e.e1.PROTECTION	Split Question	The original question "GOVTRAINING" in the 1st edition has been split into 2 sub-questions. The question text is:"The training covers data protection."

Capability (C): Civil service	C.CAPABILITIES. TRAIN.e.e1.MANAGEMENT	Split Question	The original question "GOVTRAINING" in the 1st edition has been split into 2 sub-questions. The question text is:"The training covers data management."
Capability (C): Civil service	C.CAPABILITIES. TRAIN.e.e1.DATASHARING	Split Question	The original question "GOVTRAINING" in the 1st edition has been split into 2 sub-questions. The question text is:"The training covers data sharing."
Capability (C): Civil service	C.CAPABILITIES. TRAIN.e.e1.PUBLICATION	Split Question	The original question "GOVTRAINING" in the 1st edition has been split into 2 sub-questions. The question text is:"The training covers data publication."
Capability (C): Civil service	C.CAPABILITIES. TRAIN.e.e1. ANALYSISLIMITS	Replaced	The original question "ANALYSIS" in the 1st edition has been replaced. The question text is:"The training covers data analysis and data limitations."
Capability (C): Civil service	C.CAPABILITIES. TRAIN.e.e1.AITRAINING	New Question	The new question is added into the Element subgroup "Kinds of capacities" The question text is:"The training covers artificial intelligence literacy and skills."
Capability (C): Government support for re-use	C.CAPABILITIES. GOVSUPPORT.e.e3. AIGUIDANCE	New Question	The new question is added into the Element subgroup "Specific features" The question text is:"Government support for data reuse involves public guidance on reusing data for AI or algorithmic decision-making systems."

Governance (G): Accessibility coverage & data	G.GOVERNANCE. ACCESSIBILITY.a.EXISTS_ ACCESS	Replaced	<p>The original question 'EXISTS' and 'NATURE' in the 1st edition have been replaced.</p> <p>The question text is:"Are there laws, policies, or regulations in any form requiring the inclusion of people with disabilities?"</p>
Governance (G): Accessibility coverage & data	G.GOVERNANCE. ACCESSIBILITY.e.e1. COMMS_ACCESS	New Question	<p>The new question is added into the Element subgroup "Rights and responsibilities"</p> <p>The question text is:"The framework requires the inclusion of people with disabilities with regard to communications about data matters."</p>

Annex 2-Capabilities Groups

In the second edition of the Global Data Barometer, we continue to group countries by their capacity to collect, manage, share, and use data for the public good. As in the first edition, we classify countries into three categories: lower-capability, medium-capability, and higher-capability. These groups are determined using a weighted average of 14 indicators – four primary and ten secondary – that together form the Capability component. In the first edition, this classification was based on percentile thresholds (33rd and 66th percentiles), which produced equally sized groups across a broad, globally representative set of countries.

However, this method cannot be directly applied to the second edition, which focuses specifically on 43 countries in Africa and Latin America. Given this narrower regional scope, we adopted a threshold-based approach to maintain comparability across editions. To do so, we recalculated the first edition’s capability scores using the revised indicator structure and weights introduced in the second edition. Based on this recalculation, we established fixed thresholds: countries scoring above 48.69 are classified as higher-capability, those below 31.55 as lower-capability, and those in between as medium-capability. This approach ensures that the capability groups in the second edition remain consistent with the broader global framework established in the first edition.

We then have the capabilities groups as follows:

Countries in the higher capability group	Countries in the middle capability group	Countries in the lower capability group
Argentina	Bahamas	Angola
Brazil	Barbados	Belize
Chile	Benin	Bolivia
Colombia	Costa Rica	Botswana
Dominican Republic	Ghana	Burkina Faso

Countries in the higher capability group	Countries in the middle capability group	Countries in the lower capability group
Ecuador	Guatemala	Cameroon
Mexico	Honduras	Côte d'Ivoire
Panama	Jamaica	El Salvador
Paraguay	Kenya	Gambia
Peru	Morocco	Liberia
Uruguay	South Africa	Malawi
	Trinidad and Tobago	Mozambique
	Tunisia	Namibia
		Nigeria
		Rwanda
		Senegal
		Sierra Leone
		Togo
		Uganda

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